
D5.2 / Midterm recruitment report (dBM-DEV study)

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Björn Falkenburger (TUD)	August 2024	December 2024
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Document history

Version	Date	Contributors	Action / status
0.1	09/09/2024	TUD, AUTH	Document structure (table of contents) and first draft
0.2	20/11/2024	TUD, CHUT, FIN, KCL, AUTH	Input to all sections; revisions by AUTH
0.3	22/11/2024	CHUT	Reviewed by Natalia del Campo (CHUT)
0.4	02/12/2024	FMH	Reviewed by Sofia Balula Dias (FMH)
0.5	18/12/2024	TUD	Feedback from reviews incorporated, submitted for approval by Project Coordinator
0.6	19/12/2024	AUTH	Minor revisions; Approved by the Project Coordinator for submission
1.0	19/12/2024	AUTH	Submitted version

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List of abbreviations

AUTH	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
CHUT	Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Toulouse, France
CRF	Case Report Form
dBM	Digital biomarker
dBM-DEV	Digital biomarker development validation and verification study
ESS	Epworth Sleepiness Scale
FIN	Fundacion Iniciativa para las Neurociencias, Spain
HC	Healthy control
HRA	Health Research Authority
ICF	Informed consent form
IRB	Institutional Review Board (or Ethics Committee)
iRBD	Isolated REM sleep behaviour disorder
KCL	King's College London, UK
KUL	KU Leuven
MDS-UPDRS	Movement Disorders Society - Unified Parkinson Disease Rating Scale
MoCA	Montreal Cognitive Assessment
PD	Parkinson's disease
PDQ-8	Parkinson's disease questionnaire, 8-item version
RBD	REM sleep behaviour disorder
RBDSQ	REM sleep behaviour disorder screening questionnaire
REM	Rapid eye movements
SOP	Standard operating procedure
SSOL	SmartSol
TUD	Technische Universität Dresden, Germany

Executive summary

The digital biomarkers development, validation and verification (dBM-DEV) study is a multicentre observational clinical study. The dBM-DEV study aims to: (a) develop digital biomarkers (dBM) for REM sleep behaviour disorder (RBD) and day-time somnolence, as well as to verify existing smartwatch- and smartphone-based dBM that assess motor and cognitive function, and (b) validate these dBM in a dedicated observational clinical study. For this reason, a development (~60 participants) and a confirmation (~30 participants) cohort are intended to be recruited. All procedures regarding the obtainment of ethical approval, setup of effective dissemination channels, and pre-screening requirements were collaboratively decided and issued by all study sites, namely, Technische Universität Dresden (TUD), Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Toulouse (CHUT), Fundacion Iniciativa para las Neurociencias (FIN), and King's College London (KCL).

This report gives a detailed outline of all actions performed to obtain ethical approval - including protocol modifications and amendments per clinical site - and an overview of the current patient recruitment status. All clinical sites submitted the protocol for ethical approval in December 2023, except for KCL, which was submitted in May 2024 in keeping with local procedures. Minor revisions were requested to add sample size clarifications and clarify whether the smart devices qualify as medical devices. Ad-hoc amendments were submitted in parallel referring to the addition of anthropometric information and area of living (settlement) in the Case Report Forms (CRFs), as well as to include the capture of keystroke dynamics (keyboard typing) data. Further, all screening and data collection procedures, including pre-screening questionnaires and polysomnography data collection, were issued. Standard operating procedures (SOPs) were agreed upon among clinical experts to ensure the study is carried out seamlessly and consistently across sites. Recruitment progress is presented per site, alongside the enrolled participants' key clinicodemographic information across sites. Eighteen (18) out of 60 participants for the development cohort, comprising a REM sleep behaviour disorder group and a group of healthy controls (HCs), have already been recruited. By the time of writing, clinicodemographic data for 16 out of 18 participants were collected in the clinical data management system of the study (RBD group: 13 subjects, mean age (standard deviation) 71.1 (5.3) years, 15% females / HC group: 3 subjects, mean age (standard deviation) 70.0 (10.0) years, 0% females).

1 Introduction

1.1 Document scope

This deliverable reports on the progress made on the dBM-DEV study (for further information, including the study protocol, refer to D5.1) with respect to the regulatory approval, in particular the required modifications in the protocol and the resulting amendments submitted to the ethical committees of each clinical site (i.e., TUD, CHUT, FIN, KCL). Clinical sites collaborated to develop and implement targeted recruitment strategies, and each site prepared its associated recruitment material. Clinical experts agreed on the Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), including the training material, to facilitate the seamless and efficient execution of the dBM-DEV study.

Further, the deliverable reports on the initial recruitment rate, challenges faced and mitigation strategies implemented, as well as the available cohorts at each site and the description of the current state of the dataset. Key demographic and clinical information about the study participants enrolled at the time of this report is provided in the Recruitment progress, challenges, and mitigation strategies section.

1.2 Document structure

The document includes five sections, and it is structured as follows:

- Section 1 provides a brief introduction of the deliverable.
- Section 2 reports on protocol revisions and ethical approval.
- Section 3 reports on available patient populations per site and dissemination channels.
- Section 4 provides an overview of recruitment progress, including key demographic and clinical data collected to date, as well as challenges encountered and the strategies implemented to mitigate them.
- Section 5 concludes the deliverable presenting the current state of the study.
- The Appendix lists the supplementary documents attached to this report.

2 Ethical Approvals

The most recent study protocol documents, for each site, are attached as supplementary documents (Appendix – Supplementary documents 1-4). **Table 1** outlines the initial Institutional Review Board (IRB) submissions with the associated dates. For further information regarding the contents of these submissions please refer to D5.1. **Table 2** indicates the current version of the study protocol, documented per clinical site.

Table 1 Submission dates and first responses for the initial IRB submissions at each study site, along with the corresponding protocol versions

Study site	Submission	First response	Approval	Protocol
TUD (Appendix - 1)	19 Dec 2023	11 Mar 2024	31 May 2024	1.1
CHUT (Appendix - 2)	21 Dec 2023	23 Jan 2024	06 Feb 2024	1.0
KCL (Appendix - 3)	10 May 2024	07 June 2024	09 Apr 2024	1.2
FIN (Appendix - 4)	14 Feb 2024	22 Mar /2024	08 Apr 2024	1.2

Table 2 Protocol versions currently in use at each study site, along with the approval dates

Study site	Active protocol version	Approval date
TUD	1.4	18 Nov 2024
CHUT	1.0	06 Feb 2024
KCL	1.2	04 Sep 2024
FIN	1.4	21 Oct 2024

2.1 TUD

The dBM-DEV study protocol in Germany, version 1.0, was submitted to the ethics committee of TUD on December 28, 2023, and the first response was received on March 11, 2024.

Protocol version 1.1 was submitted on March 23, 2024, incorporating the requested information on the nature of the study, specifically regarding whether the smartwatch should be classified as a medical device. Additionally, the statistical plan and sample size estimate were revised based on feedback from the ethics committee, and ethnicity was added as a demographic variable. This protocol version was approved on May 31, 2024 (BO-EK-2012024).

In addition, a protocol amendment was submitted to include keystroke dynamics as optional assessment for motor symptoms of Parkinson's disease (PD). Further revisions include collecting demographic information, namely, the assessment of rural vs urban living. It was submitted to TUD's ethics committee on August 1, 2024, as the first amendment and was approved on August 9, 2024.

The most recent protocol version (1.4) includes weight, height, and medication for all participants (not only PD patients) as demographic information.

2.2 CHUT

The dBM-DEV study protocol in French, version 1.0, was submitted to the ethics committee 'Comité de protection des personnes Île-de-France III' on December 21, 2023. The first response was received on January 23, 2024, and after providing some minor clarifications, it was swiftly approved on February 6, 2024 (2023-A02136-59).

An amendment is currently being prepared to include keystroke dynamics as an optional assessment for motor symptoms of Parkinson's disease, along with the following demographic information: ethnicity, rural versus urban living, and weight and height, to standardize the protocol across all centres.

It must be noted that in France, the submission of amendments was purposefully held off until after study initiation, in keeping with the local ethics and regulatory procedures.

2.3 FIN

The dBM-DEV study protocol in Spanish, version 1.1, was submitted to the ethics committee of Hospital Ruber Internacional, Madrid, on behalf of the Fundacion Iniciativa para las Neurociencias (FIN) on February 14, 2024, and the first response was received on March 22, 2024.

Protocol version 1.2, submitted on April 1, 2024, included the requested information on the recruitment projection for this clinical study in Spain and provided details on the source of

patient recruitment, confirming that participants would be recruited from the Movement Disorders Unit of FIN centre. This protocol version was approved on April 8, 2024 (535-Estudio dBM-DEV)

A protocol amendment was submitted (version 1.4) to introduce keystroke dynamics as an optional assessment for motor symptoms of PD and added rural versus urban living as demographic information. This version was submitted to FIN's ethics committee on September 19, 2024, and approved as the first amendment on October 21, 2024.

A second amendment is currently in preparation to also include weight and height as demographic information.

2.4 KCL

The dBM-DEV study protocol in English, version 1, was submitted to the Research Ethics Committee of the North of Scotland. The ethical review occurred during a committee meeting on June 27, 2024. Provisionally, Ethics and Health Research Authority (HRA) have provided positive conditional approval. Additional documents were provided on the patient pathway in the study, as requested during the meeting.

Full approval was granted on July 17, 2024, and approval confirmation was received from the HRA on September 4, 2024 (24/NS/0069). This approved protocol includes keystroke dynamics as an optional assessment for motor symptoms of PD and rural versus urban living as demographic information.

3 Available cohorts, dissemination channels, and pre-screening

This section addresses the recruitment of participants for the two consecutive cohorts targeted by the dBM-DEV study: (1) The development cohort, which includes patients with polysomnography-confirmed RBD and demographically matched controls, and (2) The confirmation cohort, which includes patients with PD and unknown RBD status. The dBM-DEV studies at all clinical sites were initiated as planned. For more detailed information on the eligibility criteria, refer to D5.1 (section 5). All staff involved in the studies underwent training before the study initiation using a standardized protocol (see Appendix – Supplementary document 8). The first investigator meeting was held on November 4, 2024, during which the participant recruitment schedule and the clinical partners' initial experiences with the study procedures were discussed.

3.1 TUD

TUD runs a sleep lab, headed by Dr. Tony Sehr, which has identified numerous patients with RBD in previous years, both patients with isolated RBD (iRBD) and patients with RBD in the context of other diseases, mainly PD. Patients were pre-screened for enrolment in the development cohort. Spouses and care partners will be considered healthy control participants in this study if they meet the eligibility criteria described in deliverable 5.1. Additional healthy control participants will be recruited to match the demographics of the patient cohort.

A flyer was created by AI-PROGNOSIS partners KCL and SmartSol (SSOL) (WP6) to support patient recruitment (see Appendix – Supplementary document 5). The flyer is currently being used to recruit PD patients for screening at the outpatient clinic of TUD.

3.2 CHUT

Participants for the development cohort are recruited via the registry of idiopathic RBD patients from CHUT's sleep lab, chaired by Dr. Rachel Debbs. Patients from this registry, active for over 10 years, are pre-screened according to the protocol's inclusion and exclusion criteria. Spouses and care partners of included patients are considered healthy control participants as long as they meet the eligibility criteria. To fully match the demographics of patients and healthy control participants, the control group will be further completed by enrolling eligible candidates from the active healthy control file from CHUT's Clinical Investigation Centre.

Participants for the confirmation cohort will be recruited through CHUT's PD Expert Centre, using an existing database of volunteers.

3.3 FIN

Participants for the development cohort are recruited through direct collaboration with sleep units in the Madrid (Spain) community, using a database of patients who meet the inclusion and exclusion criteria (see Appendix – Supplementary document 7). The caregivers of the participants will be included as healthy control participants as long as they meet the eligibility criteria.

Participants for the confirmation cohort will be recruited through FIN from the Movement Disorder Unit at Hospital Ruber Internacional, Madrid, Spain.

3.4 KCL

KCL health partner collaborates with a sleep lab, which has a register of numerous preidentified patients with RBD in previous years, both patients with iRBD and patients with RBD in the context of other diseases, mainly PD. Participants for the development cohort who already signed the consent form to be contacted for the future research study will be identified from this register database. Spouses and care partners will be considered as healthy control participants as long as they meet the eligibility criteria. Additional healthy participants will be identified to match demographics of the patient cohort.

KCL designed a study flyer for advertising purposes, which will be used to recruit PD patients for screening at the Movement Disorder Clinic at the Centre of Excellence in Clinical Care and Research at King's Hospital (see Appendix – Supplementary document 6).

4 Recruitment progress, challenges and mitigation strategies

The AI-PROGNOSIS clinical sites aimed to facilitate the seamless recruitment of study participants and ensure consistent conductance across clinical sites. To achieve this, an SOP for staff training was generated. The SOP, which includes guidelines for training study participants during the baseline visit, is regularly updated and included as an attached document to this report for reference (see Appendix – Supplementary document 8).

The recruitment targets for all sites combined are as follows:

Development cohort:

- 30 participants with polysomnography-confirmed RBD
- 30 healthy participants

Confirmation cohort:

- 30 patients with PD and unknown RBD status

Additionally, five participants are added to account for potential dropouts, bringing the total target to 95 participants. As of the time of submitting this deliverable, recruitment for the development cohort has been initiated. Recruitment for the confirmation cohort is expected to begin in January 2025. Details related to the confirmation cohort will be included in the upcoming deliverable D5.3 “Reporting on the status of posting results”.

Table 3 provides a summary of the recruitment process for each clinical site, while **Table 4** outlines the demographic information of the currently enrolled participants.

Table 3 Summary of recruitment progress per site, including the date of the first participant, target number of participants, current number of participants, and anticipated number of enrolments per month

Study site	Date of first participant	Target number of participants (all cohorts)	Current number of participants (all cohorts)	Anticipated number of enrolments per month
TUD	23 October 2024	30	9	4-5
CHUT	08 October 2024	15	3	2-3
FIN	15 October 2024	20	4	2-3
KCL	04 October 2024	30	2	5
Total		95	18	

Table 4 Demographic and clinical characteristics of participants in the dBM-DEV-study¹. RBD: REM sleep behaviour disorder, HC: healthy control, SD: standard deviation. MDS-UPDRS: Movement Disorders Society – Unified Parkinson’s Disease Rating Scale, MoCA: Montreal Cognitive Assessment, RBDSQ: REM Sleep Behaviour Disorder Screening Questionnaire, PDQ-8: Parkinson’s Disease Questionnaire – 8-items version.

	RBD cohort (n = 13)	HC cohort (n = 3)
Age mean (SD)	71.1 (5.3)	70.0 (10.0)
Sex - female (%)	11 males, 2 females (15%)	3 males, no females (0%)
Education (n)	Primary education = 1	Primary education = 0
	(Post-)Secondary education = 6	(Post-)Secondary education = 0
	(At least) Bachelor's degree or equivalent = 6	(At least) Bachelor's degree or equivalent = 3
Ethnicity (%)	2 Hispanic or Latino (18%)	No Hispanic or Latino participants
Racial Group	White (100%)	White (100%)
Handedness	13 right-handed (100%)	3 right-handed (100%)
MDS-UPDRS total score (SD)	13.8 (10.9)	3 (3)
MDS-UPDRS part 1 score (SD)	7.5 (5.2)	3 (3)
MDS-UPDRS part 2 score (SD)	3.3 (5.3)	0 (0)

MDS-UPDRS part 3 score (SD)	3.1 (3.3)	0 (0)
MoCA score (SD)	28.0 (2.3)	30 (1)
RBDSQ score (SD)	8.8 (1.7)	0 (0)
PDQ-8 score (SD)	3.1 (4.0)	1 (1)

¹Note: This only includes participants for whom data was available in the OpenClinica-Environment on the 18th of December 2024. As of this date, data for 16 of the 18 recruited participants in the dBM-DEV-study were available.

4.1 TUD

TUD aims to enrol 11 patients with RBD and 11 healthy participants in the development cohort, and 8 patients with PD in the confirmation cohort. As of today, 9 participants have already been enrolled in the development cohort. The anticipated enrolment rate is one participant per week, which will allow reaching the target of 50% enrolment for the development cohort (RBD patients and controls) by December 31, 2024.

4.2 CHUT

CHUT aims to enrol 5 patients with RBD and 5 healthy participants in the development cohort, and 5 patients with PD in the confirmation cohort. CHUT has so far enrolled 3 study participants into the development cohort, 2 of whom have successfully finished the study. Additionally, 2 participants from the development cohort are scheduled to be enrolled by the end of December 2024, ensuring that 50% of the site's recruitment target is met by the end of 2024.

4.3 FIN

FIN aims to enrol 6 patients with RBD and 6 healthy participants in the development cohort, and 8 patients with PD in the confirmation cohort. The enrolment strategy for FIN is 2-3 participants per month, which will allow FIN to reach the enrolment target of 50% by the end of 2024. To date, 4 participants have been recruited for the development cohort. It is expected that 1 more patient will be recruited during the month of December 2024.

4.4 KCL

KCL aims to enrol 10 patients with RBD and 10 healthy participants in the development cohort, and 10 patients with PD in the confirmation cohort. The enrolment strategy for KCL is 5 participants per month, which will allow KCL to reach the enrolment target of 50% by the end of 2024. To date, 2 participants have been recruited for the development cohort.

5 Conclusions

The key takeaways of D5.2 are as follows:

- The dBM-DEV study is a multicentre observational clinical study aiming primarily to identify smartwatch-based digital biomarkers for of detecting RBD and daytime somnolence.
- All clinical sites have actively collaborated to:

- Issue the latest version of the study protocol, incorporating all necessary updates and changes.
- Ensure local ethical approval, following IRB recommendations and required amendments,
- Develop recruitment material where needed,
- Agree on screening procedures, including staff training via SOP development, to guide staff training and ensure site consistency.
- Enrol 50% or more of the target cohort sample, demonstrating the study's growing momentum.
- All clinical sites report that the study is operational and progressing as planned, ensuring the seamless enrolment of participants into the dBM-DEV study. This marks a significant step toward achieving the study's recruitment and research objectives, focusing on ensuring quality data collection across the participating centres.
- The next steps of this study encompass the full recruitment of participants for the development cohort by the end of March 2025 and the simultaneous start of recruitment of participants for the confirmation cohort starting from January 2025, which is expected to complete enrolment by the end of June 2025. Details related to the confirmation cohort will be included in the upcoming deliverable D5.3 “Reporting on the status of posting results”.

Appendix – Supplementary documents

The following documents are attached to this report.

1. Latest ethical approval for TUD
2. Latest ethical approval for FIN
3. Latest ethical approval for CHUT
4. Latest ethical approval for KCL
5. Study flyer for TUD
6. Study flyer for KCL
7. Most current protocol version (1.4).
8. Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) document for training of study staff and participants

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Dresden, 10.11.24

**Betreff: AI-prognosis digital biomarkers development study (dBM-DEV study)
BO-EK-2012024, Amendment 2**

Sehr geehrter Damen und Herren,

Für die o.g. Studie haben sich relevante Änderungen ergeben. Um die erhobenen kinematischen Bewegungsmessungen sinnvoll auswerten zu können, ist zusätzlich zu den bisher erfassten demographischen Daten die Erfassung von Größe und Gewicht erforderlich. Zudem soll die Medikation auch bei den Teilnehmenden ohne Parkinson-Krankheit erfasst werden, um mögliche Effekte auf den Schlaf berücksichtigen zu können. Diese geringfügigen Änderungen sind erforderlich, weil wir uns aus Datenschutzgründen in der ursprünglichen Protokollversion auf ein Minimum an Daten beschränken wollten.

Zudem haben wir einen Flyer erstellt, um die Rekrutierung von Teilnehmenden zu erleichtern. Dieser wird Ihnen ebenfalls zur Prüfung vorgelegt.

BO-EK-2012024_2, Eingang 11.11.2024
An: Antragsteller/in via EP

Für Rückfragen stehe ich gerne zur Verfügung.

Mit freundlichen Grüßen

Prof. Dr. med. Björn Falkenburger

Gegen das vorgesehene Amendment / nachträgliche Änderungen bestehen keine Bedenken. Das Erstberatungsergebnis bleibt unberührt.

PD Dr. med. A. Tausche-Wunderlich
Stellv. Vorsitzende der Ethikkommission
an der Technischen Universität Dresden

Anlagen: Studienprotokoll Version 1.4, Flyer für die Rekrutierung

DICTAMEN DEL COMITÉ DE ÉTICA DE LA INVESTIGACIÓN CON MEDICAMENTOS. Estudios Observacionales

D. José Domingo García Labajo, Secretario del **Comité de Ética de la Investigación con medicamentos del Hospital Ruber Internacional de Madrid.**

CERTIFICA

Que este Comité este Comité en su reunión de fecha 21 de Octubre de 2024, ha evaluado la propuesta del **AI Prognosis**, para que se realice el estudio observacional con un producto sanitario

Identificación del Estudio

Código del Promotor: Estudio dBM-DEV	Código del CEIm HRBI: 535-Estudio dBM-DEV
Título:	<p><i>“AI-PROGNOSIS: subestudio de desarrollo de biomarcadores digitales (estudio dBM-DEV)”</i></p> <p><i>Estudio de desarrollo, validación y verificación de biomarcadores digitales (Estudio Dbm-DEV)</i></p> <p><i>AI-prognosis digital biomarkers development study (dBM-DEV study)</i></p>
Promotor:	AI Prognosis
Investigador:	Monica Kurtis
C.R.O.:	Monica Kurtis - M ^a Luisa ALMARSA

Relación de Documentos Aprobados (Versión; Fecha)

Modificación Sustancial Enmienda	Enmienda_02_V04_19Septiembre2024
Protocolo	Enmiendas al Protocolo (En- 19074 /28-535; 9/19/2024) dBM-DEV study protocol, version 1.4 dated 19/09/2024.
Hoja de Información al Participante	Versión Hoja de Información (En- 19128 /29-535; 10/21/2024) FCI dBM-DEV, versión 1.4, 19 SEP 2024.

El proyecto es un ESTUDIO OBSERVACIONAL CON MEDICAMENTOS, DE SEGUIMIENTO PROSPECTIVO.

El proyecto se plantea siguiendo los requisitos del Real Decreto 957/2020, de 3 de noviembre, por el que se regulan los estudios observacionales con medicamentos de uso humano y su realización es pertinente.

Se cumplen los requisitos necesarios de idoneidad del protocolo en relación con los objetivos del estudio y están justificados los riesgos y molestias previsibles para el sujeto, teniendo en cuenta los beneficios esperados.

El proceso de selección de los sujetos participantes es apropiado.

Se considera adecuado el procedimiento previsto para información y obtención del consentimiento informado.

Y HACE CONSTAR QUE:

Este Comité decidió emitir **DICTAMEN FAVORABLE** en la reunión celebrada el día 21 Octubre 2024 (acta nº 267).

En dicha reunión se cumplieron los requisitos establecidos en la legislación vigente y las normas de funcionamiento interno del comité para que la decisión del citado CEIm sea válida.

Que el CEIm del Hospital Ruber Internacional, tanto en su composición como en sus procedimientos, cumple con las normas de BPC (CPMP/ICH/135/95) y con la legislación vigente que regula su funcionamiento, y que la composición del CEIm es la indicada en el anexo I, teniendo en cuenta que en el caso de que algún miembro participe en el ensayo o declare algún conflicto de interés no habrá participado en la evaluación ni en el dictamen de la solicitud de autorización del ensayo clínico.

Para la realización del ensayo se consideran adecuados los centros e investigadores incluidos en el anexo II a este dictamen.

Se recuerda al investigador el requisito de solicitar a la AEMPS la publicación en el Registro Español de estudios clínicos al inicio de los estudios de seguimiento prospectivo y se recomienda para el resto de estudios observacionales con medicamentos.

Además, se recuerda que se deberá actualizar la información de seguimiento en dicha plataforma y enviar las notificaciones e informes correspondientes al CEIm.

Para que conste donde proceda, y a petición del promotor,

Fdo. José Domingo GARCÍA LABAJO

Secretario del CEIm

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Anexo I. Composición Actual del CEIm.

Composición del CEIm Hospital Ruber Internacional de Madrid	
Presidenta	Dra. Dña. Mercedes CUESTA NUIN (Directora Médico)
Vicepresidenta	Dra. Dña. M ^a del Mar GARCÍA ARENILLAS (Farmacólogo Clínico. Máster en Bioética) Ajeno a H.R.I.
Vocales	Dra. Dña. Aurora RODRÍGUEZ PÉREZ (Oncología Radioterápica).
	Dr. D. Pedro RODRÍGUEZ JIMÉNEZ (Dermatología)
	Dra. Dña. M ^a Ángeles DONOSO SANZ (Pediatría. Máster en Bioética).
	Dra. Dña. Carmen A. HARO MARQUEZ (Farmacia Hospitalaria).
	D. Carlos PADILLA MÉNDEZ (Lego en Ciencias de La Salud – Representante de los Pacientes) Ajeno a H.R.I.
	D. Isidro DÍAZ DE BUSTAMANTE Y TERMINEL (Doctor en Derecho). Ajeno a H.R.I.
	D. Alejandro MOLINA HIGUERAS (Enfermero)
	Dr. D. Jesús ESTEBAN PÉREZ (Neurología)
	Dra. Dña. Jimena RAMÓN GARCIA (Farmacéutica de Atención Primaria) Ajena a H.R.I.:
Secretario técnico	Dr. D. José Domingo GARCÍA LABAJO Medicina Intensiva

Dictamen Modificación N° 02 sobre la parte II

Anexo II – Listado de Centros Participantes

IDENTIFICACIÓN DE LA SOLICITUD

Código del Promotor: Estudio dBM-DEV	Código del CEIm HRBI: 535-Estudio dBM-DEV
<u>Título:</u>	<p><i>“AI-PROGNOSIS: subestudio de desarrollo de biomarcadores digitales (estudio dBM-DEV)”</i></p> <p><i>Estudio de desarrollo, validación y verificación de biomarcadores digitales (Estudio Dbm-DEV)</i></p> <p><i>AI-prognosis digital biomarkers development study (dBM-DEV study)</i></p>
Promotor:	AI Prognosis
C.R.O.:	Monica Kurtis M ^a Luisa ALMARSA
Modificación Sustancial Enmienda	Enmienda_02_V04_19Septiembre2024
Fecha Actualización Anexo II	21 Octubre 2024

Listado de Investigadores Principales y Centros Participantes Autorizados en España

Investigador	Centro
1. Mónica KURTIS URRRA	• Hospital Ruber Internacional de Madrid
2. María Luisa ALMARCHA MENARGUES	• Hospital Ruber Internacional de Madrid

Comité de protection des personnes Ile de France III

Avis sur une demande initiale

CPP

Nom du CPP : Comité de protection des personnes Ile de France III
Adresse : Hôpital TARNIER COCHIN - 89, rue d'Assas 75006 PARIS France
Courriel : cpp.iledefrance3@orange.fr
Téléphone : 0616191639

Promoteur / Demandeur

Promoteur : CHU de TOULOUSE
Représentant légal (UE) : -
Mandataire : -

Dossier

Numéro SI : 23.04654.000511
Numéro national : 2023-A02136-59
Référence interne : RC31/23/0184

Règlementation : Loi Jardé
Qualification : Catégorie 2

Produit ou acte : Hors produits de santé (produits non mentionnés à l'article L.5311-11 du code de la santé publique)

Investigateur : Dr FABBRI

Titre : **Etude dBM-DEV : Développement, validation et vérification de biomarqueurs numériques du trouble du comportement en sommeil paradoxal**

Ce dossier a été étudié en séance le 23/01/2024 et mandat a été donné au président du CPP d'émettre l'avis à réception des réponses du déposant aux dernières demandes. Au vu des réponses obtenues, l'avis suivant a donc été émis. Cet avis court à compter du changement de statut sur le SI.

Considérant que les conditions éthiques sont remplies notamment au regard des éléments de l'article L.1123-7 du code de la santé publique, l'examen du comité permet de conclure que la recherche peut être réalisée et de rendre l'avis suivant :

Avis favorable

Cet avis est valable deux ans. Conformément à l'article L.1123-11 du code de la santé publique, le promoteur doit déclarer au CPP le début de la recherche. Cette déclaration se fait directement sur le SIRIPH2G (bouton "démarrer l'étude").

Si vous n'avez pas été en mesure d'inclure un premier participant à la recherche dans ce délai, vous pouvez demander au CPP une prorogation de cet avis avant la fin de validité de ce dernier (article R.1123-26 du code de la santé publique).

Sur les motivations suivantes :

L'étude apparaît pertinente et le rapport bénéfices/risques acceptable.

La méthodologie est clairement décrite et adaptée aux objectifs.

Les notices d'information et de consentement sont clairement rédigés. Ils contiennent toutes les mentions.

Personnes ayant délibéré

Collège	Catégorie	Nom et prénom	Fonction
Collège I	Qualification RIPH - Biostatistique ou épidémiologie	BIGOT Thierry	
Collège I	Qualification RIPH - Biostatistique ou épidémiologie	DHOTE Robin	
Collège I	Qualification RIPH - Autre	CHRISTOFOROV Boyan	
Collège I	Qualification RIPH - Autre	LOULERGUE Pierre	Président
Collège I	Qualification RIPH - Autre	AMADOR Maria del Mar	
Collège I	Pharmacien hospitalier	PARISCOAT Guillaume	
Collège I	Auxiliaire médical	BONVALLET Bérangère	
Collège II	Compétence éthique	POLETTO-FORGET Cristina	
Collège II	Compétence éthique	DRAPEAU Julie	
Collège II	Compétence en sciences humaines et sociales ou action sociale	BESLE Sylvain	
Collège II	Compétence en sciences humaines et sociales ou action sociale	CAMUS Catherine	
Collège II	Compétence en sciences humaines et sociales ou action sociale	OLMOS Adjouani	
Collège II	Compétence juridique	SIMHON David	Vice-président
Collège II	Représentant d'association agréée	MORIN Paulette	
Collège II	Représentant d'association agréée	LAMARCHE Dominique	

Documents analysés par le CPP

Catégorie	Intitulé	Date de dépôt
ADD - Doc additionnel	<i>2023-A02136-59 DOCUMENT ADDITIONNEL DbM-DEV V1.0 du 19122023.pdf</i>	21/12/2023
ASS - Assurance	<i>2023-A022136-59 Assurance dBM-DEV.pdf</i>	21/12/2023
COU - Courrier	<i>2023-A02136-59 -Courrier Demande-V1.0 19122023 - DBM-DEV.pdf</i>	21/12/2023
CVI - CV investigateurs	<i>CV_Fabbri M Déc 2023.pdf</i>	21/12/2023
CVI - CV investigateurs	<i>CV PR RASCOL 2023.pdf</i>	21/12/2023
CVI - CV investigateurs	<i>Attestation BP Pr Rascol 2022.pdf</i>	21/12/2023
CVI - CV investigateurs	<i>BPC_MFABBRI MAI 2022 (1).pdf</i>	21/12/2023
DEM - Demande autorisation	<i>2023-A02136-59 HPS-Form-Demande-Initiale-AEC -etude dBM-DEV.pdf</i>	21/12/2023
INF - Doc Information	<i>2023-A02136-59 NIFC_dBM-DEV aidant patients MP V1.0 19122023.pdf</i>	21/12/2023
INF - Doc Information	<i>2023-A02136-59 NIFC_dBM-DEV aidant patients TCSP V1.0 19122023.pdf</i>	21/12/2023
INF - Doc Information	<i>2023-A02136-59 NIFC_dBM-DEV controle V1.0 19122023.pdf</i>	21/12/2023
INF - Doc Information	<i>2023-A02136-59 NIFC_dBM-DEV patients MP V1.0 19122023.pdf</i>	21/12/2023
INF - Doc Information	<i>2023-A02136-59 NIFC_dBM-DEV patients TCSP V1.0 19122023.pdf</i>	21/12/2023
INF - Doc Information	<i>2023-A02136-59 NIFC_dBM-DEV controle V1.1 02022024.docx</i>	02/02/2024

INF - Doc Information	<i>2023-A02136-59 NIFC_dBM-DEV aidant patients TCSP V1.1 02022024.docx</i>	02/02/2024
INF - Doc Information	<i>2023-A02136-59 NIFC_dBM-DEV aidant patients MP V1.1 02022024.docx</i>	02/02/2024
INF - Doc Information	<i>2023-A02136-59 NIFC_dBM-DEV patients TCSP V1.1 02022024.docx</i>	02/02/2024
INF - Doc Information	<i>2023-A02136-59 NIFC_dBM-DEV patients MP V1.1 02022024.docx</i>	02/02/2024
JUS - Justification lieux de recherche	<i>2023-A02136-59 Justification adequation.pdf</i>	21/12/2023
LET - Lettre	<i>Réponses au CPP.docx</i>	02/02/2024
LIS - Liste investigateurs	<i>2023-A02136-59 Liste investigateurs_dBM-DEV V1.0 19122023.pdf</i>	21/12/2023
PRO - Protocole	<i>2023-A02136-59 Protocol v1.0 19122023 dBM-DEV.pdf</i>	21/12/2023
QUE - Echelles/questionnaires	<i>2023-A02136-59 questionnaire UPDRS_French_Official_Translation_F INAL.pdf</i>	21/12/2023
RES - Résumé	<i>2023-A02136-59 Résumé_dBM-DEV V1.0 19122023.pdf</i>	21/12/2023

**Les documents étiquetés non-conformes sur le SI RIPH2G ou transmis pour information/notification dans le cadre de cette demande d'avis n'ont pas été évalués par le CPP.*

**L'intitulé des documents examinés par le comité, listés sur le présent avis, reprend la nomenclature des fichiers utilisée par le déposant sur le SI RIPH2G.*

Le 06 Février 2024

Le Président : Pierre LOULERGUE

Professor K Ray Chaudhuri
Professor of Movement Disorders
King's College London
The Maurice Wohl Clinical Neuroscience Institute
King's College London
Cutcombe Road
SE5 9RT

Email: approvals@hra.nhs.uk
HCRW.approvals@wales.nhs.uk

19 July 2024

Dear Professor Ray Chaudhuri

**HRA and Health and Care
Research Wales (HCRW)
Approval Letter**

Study title:	AI-prognosis digital biomarkers development study (dBM-DEV study)
IRAS project ID:	340929
Protocol number:	1
REC reference:	24/NS/0069
Sponsor	King's College London

I am pleased to confirm that [HRA and Health and Care Research Wales \(HCRW\) Approval](#) has been given for the above referenced study, on the basis described in the application form, protocol, supporting documentation and any clarifications received. You should not expect to receive anything further relating to this application.

Please now work with participating NHS organisations to confirm capacity and capability, in line with the instructions provided in the "Information to support study set up" section towards the end of this letter.

How should I work with participating NHS/HSC organisations in Northern Ireland and Scotland?

HRA and HCRW Approval does not apply to NHS/HSC organisations within Northern Ireland and Scotland.

If you indicated in your IRAS form that you do have participating organisations in either of these devolved administrations, the final document set and the study wide governance report (including this letter) have been sent to the coordinating centre of each participating nation. The relevant national coordinating function/s will contact you as appropriate.

Please see [IRAS Help](#) for information on working with NHS/HSC organisations in Northern Ireland and Scotland.

How should I work with participating non-NHS organisations?

HRA and HCRW Approval does not apply to non-NHS organisations. You should work with your non-NHS organisations to [obtain local agreement](#) in accordance with their procedures.

What are my notification responsibilities during the study?

The standard conditions document “[After Ethical Review – guidance for sponsors and investigators](#)”, issued with your REC favourable opinion, gives detailed guidance on reporting expectations for studies, including:

- Registration of research
- Notifying amendments
- Notifying the end of the study

The [HRA website](#) also provides guidance on these topics, and is updated in the light of changes in reporting expectations or procedures.

Who should I contact for further information?

Please do not hesitate to contact me for assistance with this application. My contact details are below.

Your IRAS project ID is **340929**. Please quote this on all correspondence.

Yours sincerely,

Rachel Katzenellenbogen

Approvals Specialist

List of Documents

The final document set assessed and approved by HRA and HCRW Approval is listed below.

<i>Document</i>	<i>Version</i>	<i>Date</i>
Evidence of Sponsor insurance or indemnity (non NHS Sponsors only) [Sponsor Indemnity certificate]		01 August 2023
IRAS Application Form	340929/1676 683/37/649	07 June 2024
Letter from funder [Grant letter - Funder]		03 October 2023
Other [RGF approval letter]		27 March 2024
Other [Researcher response email]		17 July 2024
Participant consent form [ICF RBD confirmation with PD]	4	01 July 2024
Participant consent form [ICF RBD development cohort]	4	01 July 2024
Participant consent form [ICF Carer of development cohort RBD]	4	01 July 2024
Participant consent form [ICF development cohort control participant]	4	01 July 2024
Participant information sheet (PIS) [PIS for RBD development cohort]	4	01 July 2024
Participant information sheet (PIS) [PIS for Development cohort control participant]	4	01 July 2024
Participant information sheet (PIS) [PIS for RBD confirmation with PD]	4	01 July 2024
Participant information sheet (PIS) [PIS for carer of development cohort]	4	01 July 2024
Research protocol or project proposal [Protocol]	4	17 July 2024
Sample diary card/patient card [Script]	1	10 June 2024
Summary CV for Chief Investigator (CI) [Prof Ray Chaudhuri]		22 July 2020
Summary of any applicable exclusions to sponsor insurance (non-NHS sponsors only) [Sponsor Indemnity]		01 August 2023
Validated questionnaire [Clinical Report Form A: SOCIO DEMOGRAPHIC DATA; PD-RELATED HISTORY; Medical history]	Form A	26 March 2024
Validated questionnaire [Clinical Report Form B: Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCa); MDS-UPDRS; ESS & RBDSQ]	Form B	26 March 2024
Validated questionnaire [Epworth sleepiness scale]		
Validated questionnaire [The MDS-sponsored Revision of the Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale]		
Validated questionnaire [REM Behavioural sleeping scale]		

Information to support study set up

The below provides all parties with information to support the arranging and confirming of capacity and capability with participating NHS organisations in England and Wales. This is intended to be an accurate reflection of the study at the time of issue of this letter.

Types of participating NHS organisation	Expectations related to confirmation of capacity and capability	Agreement to be used	Funding arrangements	Oversight expectations	HR Good Practice Resource Pack expectations
<p>This is a non-commercial single site study taking place in the NHS where that single NHS organisation's partner University is the study sponsor therefore there is only one site type.</p>	<p>This is a single site study sponsored by that single NHS organisation's partner University. You should work with the sponsor/JRO R&D office to make arrangements to set up the study. The sponsor/JRO R&D office will confirm to you when the study can start following issue of HRA and HCRW Approval.</p>	<p>This is a non-commercial single site study taking place in the NHS where that single NHS organisation's partner University is the study sponsor. Therefore no study agreements are required.</p>	<p>Study funding arrangements are detailed in A65 of the IRAS form.</p>	<p>A Principal Investigator should be appointed at participating NHS organisations of this type.</p>	<p>Where an external individual who does not already hold an NHS employment contract will be conducting polysomnography, then they would be expected to hold an Honorary Research Contract. This should be issued be on the basis of a Research Passport (if university employed) or an NHS to NHS confirmation of pre-engagement checks letter (if NHS employed). These should confirm Occupational Health Clearance, enhanced DBS checks and appropriate barred list checks.</p> <p>External staff holding pre-existing NHS employment contracts, or staff only undertaking any other research activities that will be undertaken at this site type should obtain a Letter of Access. This should be issued be on the basis of a Research Passport (if university employed) or an NHS to NHS</p>

					confirmation of pre-engagement checks letter (if NHS employed). These should confirm Occupational Health Clearance and standard DBS checks.
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Other information to aid study set-up and delivery

This details any other information that may be helpful to sponsors and participating NHS organisations in England and Wales in study set-up.

The applicant has indicated they intend to apply for inclusion on the NIHR CRN Portfolio.

ai-prognosis

AI-PROGNOSIS: Studie zur Entwicklung digitaler Biomarker (dBM-DEV-Studie)

Haben Sie eine REM-Schlaf-Verhaltensstörung?

Die REM-Schlaf-Verhaltensstörung (RBD) ist ein Zustand, bei dem man im Traumschlaf um sich schlägt oder ruft. Sie stellt einen Risikofaktor für die spätere Entwicklung einer Parkinson-Krankheit dar. Traditionell wird RBD in spezialisierten Schlaflabors diagnostiziert, in denen Patienten eine oder mehrere Nächte verbringen. In der dBM-DEV-Studie untersuchen wir, ob eine RBD auch zu Hause – beim Schlafen im eigenen Bett – festgestellt werden kann.

RBD

Dazu sollen in dieser Studie eine Reihe neuartiger digitaler Biomarker für die Erkennung von RBD anhand von Aufzeichnungen einer Smartwatch entwickelt werden. Konkret sollen aus passiven Smartwatch-Daten Merkmale identifiziert werden, die mit Episoden von RBD assoziiert sind. Es soll gezeigt werden, dass diese Merkmale Episoden von RBD zuverlässig erkennen können.

Für die Teilnahme benötigen Sie ein Android-Smartphone. Für die Dauer der Studie bekommen die Teilnehmenden eine Smartwatch gestellt. Reisekosten werden erstattet.

Universitäts ParkinsonCentrum Dresden

Klinik und Poliklinik für Neurologie

Studienambulanz

Unter www.neurostudien.uniklinikum-dresden.de (einfach QR-Code scannen) können Sie sich über aktuelle Studien informieren und sich bei Interesse anmelden. Unser Studienteam meldet sich dann bei Ihnen.

Ansprechpartner:

Prof. Björn Falkenburger
Dr. med. Nils Schnalke
Dipl. Psych. Tim Feige
Tel. 0351 458 11544
E-Mail studien-neurologie@ukdd.de

Hier finden sie uns:

Hochschulambulanz der Klinik für Neurologie
Uniklinikum Dresden, Haus 27 (DINZ)
Fetscherstrasse 74
1. OG, Leitstelle F
01307 Dresden

Gemeinsame Studienambulanz
Hochschulmedizin und DZNE Dresden
Tatzberg 41, EG links
01307 Dresden

Funded by
the European Union

AI-PROGNOSIS wird von der Europäischen Union im Rahmen der Finanzhilfvereinbarung Nr. 101080581 finanziert.

Finanziert von der Europäischen Union. Die geäußerten Ansichten und Meinungen sind jedoch ausschließlich die des Autors/der Autoren und spiegeln nicht unbedingt die der Europäischen Union oder der Europäischen Exekutivagentur für Gesundheit und Digitales wider. Weder die Europäische Union noch die Europäische Exekutivagentur für Gesundheit und digitale Medien können für sie verantwortlich gemacht werden.

ai.prognosis: digital biomarkers development study (dBM-DEV study)

Do you have REM Behavioural disorder (sleep disorder)?

Rapid eye movement (REM) sleep behaviour disorder (RBD) is a condition in which you act out your dreams while you sleep. These dreams are often very vivid and can involve a wide range of movements. Unlike sleepwalking or night terrors, you can recall your dreams upon waking.

RBD

The main objective of this study is to identify a novel, robust dBM for the detection of RBD using smartwatch-based recordings of passive data. Specifically, this study aims to identify features extracted from passive smartwatch data that are associated with episodes of RBD and demonstrate that these features can potentially help increase specificity of RBD detection.

Study participation travel expenses will be reimbursed on request. Thank you for your time reading this information.

Study contact:

Study Chief investigator: Prof K Ray Chaudhuri MBBS MD FRCP (Lond) FRCP (Edin) DSc FEAN

Dhaval Trivedi (dhaval.trivedi1@nhs.net) Project coordinator/clinical research fellow

Aleksandra Podlewska (aleksandra.podlewska@nhs.net)

Phoebe Tall (phoebe.tall@nhs.net) Project administrator

AI-PROGNOSIS: Digital biomarkers development substudy (dBM-DEV study)

Study protocol

Funded by the
European Union

Person who directs and supervises the research:

Prof. Dr. med. Björn Falkenburger
Klinik und Poliklinik für Neurologie
Universitätsklinikum „Carl Gustav Carus“
Fetscherstraße 74 | 01307 Dresden

Methodology and Data Management:

Prof. Dr. med. Björn Falkenburger
Klinik und Poliklinik für Neurologie
Universitätsklinikum „Carl Gustav Carus“
Fetscherstraße 74 | 01307 Dresden

HISTORY OF PROTOCOL UPDATES

Version	Author	Date	Reason for update
0.9	BF	27 NOV 2023	last common English version
1.0	BF	19 DEC 2023	submitted version
1.1	BF	18 APR 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• study title changed from “AI-prognosis digital biomarkers development study (dBM-DEV study)” to “AI-PROGNOSIS: Digital biomarkers development substudy (dBM-DEV study)” to reflect the fact that dBM-DEV is a substudy of the AI-PROGNOSIS study• clarification of the study purpose with respect to MDR as requested by TUD’s IRB• clarification of statistical planning as requested by TUD’s IRB, changed main outcome criterion 20% to 40%• ethnicity is recorded as required by the EU• question about RBD episode added to study protocol (previously in ICF)
1.2	BF	09 MAY 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• keystone dynamics added as optional outcome

1.3	BF	07 July 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the question whether study participants reside in an urban or rural environment is recorded to report diversity of the study population as required by the EU. the clinicaltrials.gov entry was adapted to the version accepted by the repository
1.4	BF	10 Nov 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> height and weight were added as demographic variables because they are necessary for analysis of kinematic digital biomarkers (page 19 and 21) medication is recorded not only for patients with PD, but for all participants (page 19)

PROTOCOL SIGNATURE PAGE

AI-PROGNOSIS: Digital biomarkers development substudy (dBM-DEV study)

Person who directs and supervises the research

Prof. Dr. med. Björn Falkenburger

Klinik und Poliklinik für Neurologie

Universitätsklinikum „Carl Gustav Carus“

Fetscherstraße 74 | 01307 Dresden

Tel: +49 351 458 2532, Fax: +49 351 458-4352

Email: bfalken@ukdd.de

Dresden, on: 10 November 2024 Prof. Dr. med. Björn Falkenburger

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List of abbreviations

CHUT	Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Toulouse, France
dbM	Digital biomarker
ESS	Epworth Sleepiness Scale
FIN	Fundacion Iniciativa para las Neurociencias, Spain
KCL	King's College London, UK
MDS-UPDRS	Movement Disorders Society – Unified Parkinson Disease Scale
MoCA	Montreal Cognitive Assessment
PD	Parkinson's disease
PDQ-8	Parkinson's disease questionnaire, 8-item version
RBD	REM sleep behaviour disorder
RBDSQ	REM sleep behaviour disorder screening questionnaire
REM	Rapid eye movements
TUD	Technische Universität Dresden, Germany

1 Summary of the research

PERSON WHO DIRECTS AND SUPERVISES THE RESEARCH	Prof. Dr. med. Björn Falkenburger Klinik und Poliklinik für Neurologie Universitätsklinikum „Carl Gustav Carus“ Fetscherstraße 74 01307 Dresden
Title	AI-PROGNOSIS: Digital biomarkers development, validation and verification substudy (dBM-DEV study)
JUSTIFICATION/ CONTEXT	REM sleep behaviour disorder (RBD) is the best predictor for neurodegenerative diseases with synuclein pathology, including Parkinson's disease (PD). Yet, RBD only affects 0.5-1 % of the general population. It can only be confirmed by polysomnography, which is a cumbersome procedure that cannot be used for screening. A RBD screening questionnaire (RBDSQ) has been developed which has high sensitivity but low specificity.
Primary Objective	The main objective of this study is to identify a novel, robust dBM for the detection of RBD using smartwatch-based recordings of passive data. Specifically, this study aims to identify features extracted from passive smartwatch data that are associated with episodes of RBD and demonstrate that these features can potentially help increase specificity of RBD detection as compared to the score of the RBD screening questionnaire (RBDSQ).
Secondary Objectives	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. demonstrate that sensitivity of RBD detection can be improved via dBM measurements as compared to the score of the RBD screening questionnaire. 2. identify mobility patterns (features) that correlate with the extent of daytime somnolence as reported by the score of the Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS). 3. verify feasibility to acquire dBM for motor symptoms (bradykinesia, tremor and dyskinesias, gait, posture) and non-motor symptoms (cognition) 4. evaluate the performance of the dBM's correcting for age and sex.
OUTLINE OF THE RESEARCH	This is a multicentre observational research study.

	<p>The study is conducted stepwise on two subsequent cohorts referred to as the development cohort (comprising 30 patients with RBD and 30 matched controls) and the confirmation cohort (comprising 30 patients with PD). Following a baseline visit, participants will undergo daily-life dBM tracking over a duration of 4 weeks and 3 months, respectively. Additionally, PD patients enrolled in the confirmation cohort will receive a polysomnography.</p> <p>The investigation is conducted in four European sites. Each site will submit this protocol to their local ethics committee.</p>
Inclusion Criteria	<p><u>Participants of the “Development cohort”:</u></p> <p>RBD patients:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Age: >18 years ● Written declaration of informed consent ● The participant is using a compatible smartphone, a smartwatch will be provided for the duration of the study ● The participant has a care partner with whom they share their bedroom at night ● Known RBD as defined by the International Classification of Sleep Disorders (ICSD-3) as demonstrated by polysomnography with at least one episode of RBD per week (on average over the last month, frequency reported with the help of the care partner). <p>Healthy matched controls:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Healthy volunteers demographically matched to the enrolled RBD patients. ● Written declaration of informed consent ● The participant is using a compatible smartphone; a smartwatch will be provided for the duration of the study. ● No history of RBD. <p><u>Participants of the “Confirmation cohort”:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Age: >18 years. ● Diagnosis of PD ● RBDSQ score 3 – 12 points

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Absence of dementia • Written informed consent • The participant is using a compatible smartphone, a smartwatch will be provided for the duration of the study • Participants have a care partner.
Exclusion criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inability to consent for study procedures as judged by the investigator. • Lacking motivation to participate in study procedures as judged by the investigator. • Lack of social security.
Main Evaluation Criterion	<p>As the primary outcome measure, we will determine the number of nights with dBM features reported by the smartwatch that in the development cohort correlated with the occurrence of RBD episodes.</p> <p>The study will be considered positive if RBD-associated features are not observed in at least 40% of participants with an RBDSQ score above the threshold of 6 points but no diagnosis of RBD as confirmed by polysomnography.</p>
Secondary Evaluation Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spearman correlation coefficient between smartwatch-based features and the Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS) - continuity of motion tracking for analysis of motor dBM - number and quality of acquired videos for analysis of gait and posture - number of completed cognitive tasks - duration of the custom virtual keyboard usage - correlation coefficients corrected for age and sex
Study size	<p>A total of 90 participants will be enrolled in the study across the two subsequent cohorts, including 30 RBD patients and matched 30 controls in the “development cohort” and 30 patients with PD in the “confirmation cohort”.</p>
DURATION OF THE RESEARCH	<p>Development cohort:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Duration of the recruitment period: 6 months - Follow-up period per participant: 4 weeks - Total research duration: 7 months <p>Confirmation cohort:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Duration of the recruitment period: 6 months- Follow-up period per participant: 3 months- Total research duration: 9 months
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE DATA	Prof. Dr. med. Björn Falkenburger Klinik und Poliklinik für Neurologie Universitätsklinikum „Carl Gustav Carus“ Fetscherstraße 74 01307 Dresden
EXPECTED BENEFITS	It is hoped that the identification of robust dBMs in this study will have a favourable impact on the PD community in the future by enabling the daily-life detection and monitoring of PD symptoms, including the early signs of the disease such as RBD.

REGISTRATION

This research has been registered at <http://www.clinicaltrials.gov/> on June 6, 2024 as NCT06444789.

2 SCIENTIFIC JUSTIFICATION AND GENERAL DESCRIPTION

2.1 Current state of knowledge

Parkinson's disease (PD) is the second most common neurodegenerative disease. It is caused by Lewy pathology spreading through the nervous system, which results in a number of motor and non-motor symptoms (Dinter et al. 2020). Digital technologies can potentially support diagnosis and treatment of PD by providing objective and continual data about motor and non-motor features of the disease. For instance, smartwatch and smartphone -based features can be used for home-based reporting of motor fluctuations (Powers et al. 2021), tremor, dyskinesias (Sieberts et al. 2023), fine motor impairment (Iakovakis et al. 2018), but also for assessment of cognitive function (Dagum 2018).

The digital biomarker development (dBM-Dev) study presented here is part of a four-year HORIZON research programme entitled AI PROGNOSIS aiming to advance PD diagnosis and care by (1) developing novel, predictive AI models for personalised PD risk assessment and prognosis (in terms of time to higher disability transition and response to medication) based on multi-source patient records and databases, including in-depth health, phenotypic and genetic data, (2) implementing a system of digital biomarkers informing the AI models by tracking key risk/progression markers in daily living, and ultimately (3) translating the models and digital biomarkers into a validated, privacy-aware, AI-driven toolkit, supporting healthcare professionals (HCPs) in disease screening, monitoring and treatment optimization, via quantitative, explainable evidence, and empowering individuals with/without PD with tailored insights for informed health management.

Within this broader framework, the aim of the current dBM-DEV study is to develop the digital biomarkers that will be used in two subsequent well-powered clinical studies designed to validate the aforementioned AI-PROGNOSIS toolkit. Development of digital, home-based assessments for motor and cognitive function can build on a significant body of published evidence to which consortium partners have contributed (Dias et al. 2017; Mahboobeh et al. 2022; Dias et al. 2020; Iakovakis et al. 2018; 2020; Kyritsis, Diou, and Delopoulos 2019; Papadopoulos et al. 2020). In contrast, the literature about detection of (REM) sleep behaviour disorder (RBD) by digital, home-based assessments is much more limited. For this reason, development of a digital biomarker (dBM) for RBD was chosen as the primary objective of the dBM-DEV study, whereas the verification of dBM for motor and cognitive symptoms are under secondary objectives.

RBD is the most important predictor for PD known today, and an accurate identification of individuals with prodromal PD is crucial to test and apply neuroprotective treatments. RBD only affects 0.5-1 % of the general population (Sasai-Sakuma et al. 2020; Haba-Rubio et al. 2018; Kang et al. 2013). Current practice relies on a screening questionnaire and

confirmation by polysomnography. The sensitivity of the RBD screening questionnaire (RBDSQ) is high (0.96) 9,19, but its specificity is only 0.56 (Stiasny-Kolster et al. 2007). This means that 44% of patients without RBD will have a positive RBDSQ. If one wanted to use the RBDSQ to detect RBD as a predictor for PD in the general population, 44% of the population would need to undergo polysomnography. This is not feasible due to cost and availability of sleep laboratories. In addition, the validity of the RBDSQ in early PD has been put into question (Halsband et al. 2018). Thus, there is thus a need for a confirmatory test to identify patients with a high risk for RBD to undergo polysomnography. One recent study used a three-step process based on an accelerometer and heart-rate data recorded from a smartwatch to first detect sleep/awake state, then identify the sleep stage, and finally movements during REM sleep (Ko et al. 2022; Auepanwiriyaikul et al. 2020).

2.2. Research hypotheses

To be tested in the development cohort

In participants with known RBD, night-time mobility will be recorded using smartwatch inertial sensors. Features will be extracted from the raw data and analysed in concert with additional biomarkers (blood pressure, heart rate). We hypothesise that specific patterns of movement correlate with the occurrence of RBD episodes as reported with the help of care partners. This hypothesis also implies that these patterns are not detected in study participants without RBD.

Daytime mobility will also be recorded by the smartwatch inertial sensors. We hypothesise that specific patterns of reduced mobility correlate with the extent of daytime somnolence as reported by the score of the Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS). Similarly, we hypothesise that specific patterns of increased mobility correlate with the extent of tremor and dyskinesias as reported by the respective scores of the Movement Disorders Society - Unified Parkinson Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS).

In addition to these passive measurements, participants will also be given instructions to perform active motor tests related to posture, balance, gait, and leg agility. Skeleton tracking data will be collected from participants via smartphone camera. Finally, participants will be asked to perform short cognitive tests on their smartphone. Features extracted from this interaction with the smartphone include not only the percentage of correct answers, but also reaction times and their variances. These assessments for motor and non-motor symptoms of PD will be performed to verify feasibility of dBM assessment.

To be tested in the confirmation cohort:

The RBDSQ is a screening instrument. Hence it is characterised by high sensitivity and low specificity.

We will record passive data in study participants with an RBDSQ score of 3-12 points, thus around the cut-off value of 6 points. We hypothesise that the features extracted from these recordings can potentially help increase sensitivity and specificity of the RBDSQ. Specifically, we hypothesise that features associated with RBD episodes in the development cohort are not present in all participants with an RBDSQ score just above the cut-off, i.e. with 6-12 points. In addition, these features might be present in some of the participants with an RBDSQ score just below the cut-off, i.e., with 3-6 points.

Daytime mobility will again be recorded by the smartwatch inertial sensors. Any correlation observed between features of daytime mobility with daytime somnolence as reported by the ESS will be reassessed using the recordings obtained in the confirmation cohort. dBM for motor and non-motor symptoms of PD will be acquired as in the development cohort to verify feasibility of these assessments.

2.3. Justification of the methodological choices

Development cohort

RBD occurs at night and is characterised by movements of arms and legs during REM sleep. These movements cannot be detected by a smartphone alone; we will therefore supply study participants with a smartwatch (to be worn on the side where patients usually wear a watch). From the smartwatch, we will use the inertial sensors to detect the movements. In addition, we will use the recorded cordial data (e.g. heart rate) to properly attribute the movement to the correct sleep stages.

RBD episodes do not occur every night. In order to remain efficient and not burden participants unnecessarily, we will only include patients with more than 1 episode per week (on average).

RBD can only be detected with certainty in polysomnography. Yet, episodes do not occur every night and people often do not sleep well in the sleep lab. For this reason, we defined as the “ground truth” RBD episodes reported with the help of care partners in patients in which RBD was previously confirmed by polysomnography.

In order to support the identification of the correct stretches of the night, the first two participants will undergo polysomnography (at any time during the course of the study). This will allow detection of the REM sleep phases and facilitate the development of the dBM.

Confirmation cohort

In order to remain efficient, we chose not to include patients in the confirmation cohort with a very high RBDSQ score. Because they already have a very high likelihood for RBD,

adding a dBM is not likely to add relevant information. Similarly, we chose not to include participants with a very low score on the RBDSQ because they have a very low probability for RBD, and a dBM is unlikely to add relevant information.

In order to make sure participants can comply with study procedures, we chose to include only participants with MoCA > 24 points.

RBD episodes do not occur every night. In order to make sure the dBM has the potential to detect RBD episodes, the study duration was set to 3 months.

RBD is diagnosed by polysomnography. This diagnostic procedure was therefore chosen as the gold standard for the dBM development.

2.4. Expected benefits

It is hoped that the identification of robust dBM in this study will have a favourable impact on the PD community in the future by enabling the daily-life detection and monitoring of PD symptoms, including the early signs of the disease such as RBD.

Objectives

Main objective

The main objective of this study is to identify a novel, robust dBM for the detection of RBD using smartwatch-based recordings of passive data.

Specifically, we aim to identify features extracted from passive smartwatch data collection that are associated with episodes of RBD and demonstrate that these features can potentially help increase specificity of RBD detection as compared to the score of the RBD screening questionnaire (RBDSQ).

The identified features will be independent of the device used for recording. One example could be the number of wrist movements during the second half of the night relative to the number of wrist movements during the first half of the night.

Secondary objectives

1. In extension to the primary objective, we aim to demonstrate that sensitivity of RBD detection can potentially be improved via dBM measurements as compared to the score of the RBD screening questionnaire.

2. We aim to identify mobility patterns (features) that correlate with the extent of daytime somnolence as reported by the score of the Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS)¹⁰.
3. We aim to verify feasibility to acquire dBM for motor symptoms (tremor, bradykinesia, dyskinesias, gait, posture) and non-motor symptoms (cognition).
4. We aim to evaluate the performance of the dBM's correcting for age and sex.

3 Research design

AI-PROGNOSIS is a multicentre observational research study. The dBM-DEV substudy is conducted stepwise on two subsequent cohorts referred to as the development cohort (comprising 30 patients with RBD and 30 matched controls) and the confirmation cohort (comprising 30 patients with PD). Following a baseline visit, participants will undergo daily-life dBM tracking over a duration of 4 weeks and 3 months, respectively. Additionally, PD patients enrolled in the confirmation cohort will receive a polysomnography.

The investigation is conducted in four European sites (UK, France, Germany and Spain). Each site will submit this protocol to their local ethics committee.

Abbreviation	Site address	Principal Investigator
CHUT	CHU University Hospital Toulouse, place du Dr Baylac, 31059, Toulouse, France	Margherita Fabbri
FIN	Hospital Ruber Internacional, Calle La Masó 38, 28034, Madrid, Spain	Monica Kurtis
KCL	KING'S COLLEGE LONDON STRAND, LONDON WC2R 2LS, United Kingdom	Dhaval Trivedi
TUD	Technische Universität Dresden Klinik für Neurologie Fetscherstrasse 74 Germany	Björn Falkenburger

5. ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

5.1. Inclusion criteria

“Development cohort”, inclusion criteria for participants with RBD

- Age: >18 years
- Written declaration of informed consent (see Annex 1).
- The participant is using a smartphone compatible with the smartwatch that will be provided for the duration of the study.
- The participant is able to use the smartphone, smartwatch and study app – as judged by investigator
- Wifi available at the participant’s home to upload smartwatch data.
- Known RBD as defined by the *International Classification of Sleep Disorders (ICSD-3)* (Sateia 2014) confirmed by polysomnography
- The participant has a care partner with whom they share their bedroom at night
- Ability to provide information after each night whether an RBD episode occurred, with the help of their care partner
- At least one episode of RBD per week (on average over the last month).
- A diagnosis of PD is not required.

“Development cohort”, inclusion criteria for controls

- Age (+/- 5 years)- and sex-matched control for a participant with known RBD
- Age: >18 years
- Written declaration of informed consent (see Annex 2).
- The participant is using a smartphone compatible with the smartwatch that will be provided for the duration of the study.
- The participant is able to use the smartphone, smartwatch and study app – as judged by investigator
- Wifi available at the participant’s home to upload smartwatch data.

“Confirmation cohort”, inclusion criteria for participants

- Age: >18 years.
- Diagnosis of PD based on the criteria published by the Movement Disorders Society (Postuma et al. 2015)

- Absence of dementia (defined as MoCA score ≥ 24) to ensure compliance with study procedures and ability to consent for study procedures. MoCA: Montreal Cognitive Assessment (Nasreddine et al. 2005)
- Written declaration of informed consent (see Annex 4)
- The participant is using a smartphone compatible with the smartwatch that will be provided for the duration of the study
- The participant has a care partner
- The participant is able to use the smartphone, smartwatch and study app – as judged by investigator
- RBDSQ score 3 - 12 points (Stiasny-Kolster et al. 2007)
- The medication for PD and sleep has not been changed during the past 4 weeks.

Exclusion criteria, all cohorts

- Inability to consent for study procedures, e.g., due to cognitive decline, as judged by the investigator.
- Lacking motivation to participate in study procedures – as judged by the investigator.
- Participants who are not affiliated to their country's social security health system
- Participant under adult autonomy protection system, legal guardianship or incapacitation.

Feasibility and recruitment procedures

For both cohorts, participants will be recruited from the movement disorders outpatient clinics of the neurology department of each site. Healthy participants will be recruited by outreach activities that include conventional media (like newspapers) and social media. Material will be provided to the Ethics committee as it becomes available.

RBD only affects 0.5-1 % of the general population. In order to ensure a sufficiently high number of participants with RBD in the development cohort, we will mainly draw on the existing cohorts of RBD patients in each study site.

Procedures of the research

Screening and enrolment

Prospective participants will be informed about the study and will receive a participant information sheet and informed consent form approved by the appropriate ethics committee, describing the study, and providing sufficient information to allow them to make an informed decision about their participation, after adequate reflection time and prior to any assessment. If the participants have further questions about the study, these will be answered by the local study team at any time, on site or via remote communication (telephone or email).

Patients' care partners will be provided an information sheet explaining the study, as well as their role in helping patients provide the information required. The information sheet will include an optional statement of opposition, which care partners may sign should they object to the study.

After providing consent participants will be screened for inclusion and exclusion criteria. Gender will also be considered to ensure that groups are balanced, as a 1.5 to 1 ratio of male to female participants is foreseen, i.e., the same ratio observed for patients with PD in the general population.

In the confirmation cohort, after providing consent to participate in the study, patients will perform a MoCA test to confirm that dementia is not present. Results from a previous MoCA test may be used if collected less than 24 weeks prior to the patient signing the informed consent form. RBDSQ will be conducted after the MoCA. Patients with RBDSQ scores below 3 or above 12 will be excluded in order to avoid burdening patients with biomarker assessment and polysomnography for which dBMs are unlikely to change the result provided by the RBDSQ.

Study procedures in the development cohort

During baseline, the following demographic data will be registered: age, sex, education, handedness, ethnicity, size of town of residence, **weight, height, current medication (if any)**. The following assessments will be obtained:

- RBD screening questionnaire (RBDSQ) (Stiasny-Kolster et al. 2007)
- Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS) (Johns 1991)
- MDS-UPDRS I-IV, including the Hoehn and Yahr (HY) staging (Goetz et al. 2008)
- Parkinson's disease questionnaire, 8-item version (PDQ-8) (Peto et al., 1998)

If a participant is diagnosed with PD, the following information will be registered: year of first symptom, year of introduction of antiparkinsonian treatments, PD subtype (Stebbins et al. 2013), more strongly affected side.

The following commercially available smartwatch will be provided to each study participant with the official documentation (booklet): Withings Scanwatch (compatible with iOS and Android smartphones, see below for details), or equivalent. The study app will be installed on the participants' smartphone. This will be done by the study participant, with the support of study personnel if needed. The participant will be trained to set the time of day for the question about an RBD episode during the previous night, and on how to set up and use the custom virtual keyboard, which has been developed for the collection of keystroke dynamics. In addition, the Withings app will be installed on the participants' smartphone.

Each participant will be assigned a coded pseudonym consisting of the study site (e.g. "TUD") and a random number. This pseudonym will be noted on the enrolment log. This pseudonym will be used for registration on the study app and in the Withings app. No personal data (name, email, phone number) will be entered in either app. The study app is described in more detail below.

Participants will be instructed to wear the smartwatch as much as possible during day and night for 4 weeks. The predicted battery life for the smartwatch is 3 weeks. Every day, at a time specified by the study participants, they will be asked to respond with the help of their caregiver whether they likely had an episode of RBD during the previous night.

In addition, participants will perform active tests: Every two weeks, patients will be asked to acquire, with the help of their care partners, a short video of themselves while they tap their feet, rise from a chair, stand and walk. Moreover, patients will be asked to perform three brief cognitive tasks: N-back test, balloon analogue risk task, stop-signal task.

Data from smartwatch and smartphone will be transferred to the study cloud whenever the participant has access to wifi. An avatar will be fitted to each video after acquisition. Only the avatar will be stored and transferred to the study cloud. Video data will not be stored in the study app or transmitted to the study cloud.

Patients will be called after 2 weeks by the study team to ask for problems or questions and every four weeks after that.

The first two patients of each study site will undergo polysomnography for one night to facilitate calibration of the digital biomarker for RBD. This will be scheduled based on availability during the course of the study.

At the end of the study, the smartwatch will be returned to the study centre and all apps will be uninstalled. If a participant is not able to return the smartwatch, they will be provided with a shipping envelope.

Study procedures in the confirmation cohort

A flowchart of the study procedures in the confirmation cohort is provided in Figure 1. Since the MoCA test for cognitive impairment is an exclusion criterion, but also a study procedure, it is performed after informed consent.

Figure 1: Flow of study procedures for the confirmation cohort

After providing informed consent, PD patients will be tested for cognition using the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA), version 7.1 with lion (Nasreddine et al. 2005). Patients with scores <24 will be excluded. Patients with scores ≥ 24 will fill out the RBDSQ (Stiasny-Kolster et al. 2007). Patients with RBDSQ scores <3 and patients with scores >12 will be excluded. All other patients will undergo an assessment of general characteristics, including demographics (age, sex, education, handedness, ethnicity, size of town of residence, height, weight), year of first symptom, year of introduction of antiparkinsonian treatments, PD subtype (Stebbins et al. 2013), more strongly affected side, medication schedule.

Moreover, the following clinical assessments will be performed at baseline:

- MDS-UPDRS I-IV, including the Hoehn and Yahr (HY) staging (Goetz et al. 2008)
- Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS) (Johns 1991)
- Parkinson's disease questionnaire, 8-item version (PDQ-8) (Peto et al., 1998)

The following commercially available smartwatch will be provided to each study participant with the official documentation (booklet): Withings Scanwatch (compatible with iOS and Android smartphones, see below for details), or equivalent. The study app will be installed on the participants' smartphone. This will be done by the study participant, with the support of study personnel if needed. The participant will be trained to set the time of day for the question about an RBD episode during the previous night, and on how to set up and use the custom virtual keyboard, which has been developed for the collection of keystroke dynamics. In addition, the Withings app will be installed on the participants' smartphone.

Each participant will be assigned a coded pseudonym consisting of the study site (e.g. "TUD") and a random number. This pseudonym will be noted on the enrolment log. This pseudonym will be used for registration on the study app and in the Withings app. No personal data (name, email, phone number) will be entered in either app. The study app is described in more detail below.

Participants will be instructed to wear the smartwatch as much as possible during day and night for 3 months. The predicted battery life for the smartwatch is 3 weeks. Every day, at a time specified by the study participants, they will be asked to respond with the help of their caregiver whether they likely had an episode of RBD during the previous night.

In addition, participants will perform active tests: Every two weeks, patients will be asked to acquire, with the help of their care partners, a short video of themselves while they tap their feet, rise from a chair, stand and walk. Moreover, patients will be asked to perform three brief cognitive tasks: N-back test, balloon analogue risk task, stop-signal task.

Data from smartwatch and smartphone will be transferred to the study cloud whenever the participant has access to wifi. An avatar will be fitted to each video after acquisition. Only the avatar will be stored and transferred to the study cloud. Video data will not be stored in the study app or transmitted to the study cloud.

Patients will be called after 2 weeks by the study team to ask for problems or questions and every four weeks after that.

During the course of the study, each participant will undergo polysomnography. This will be scheduled during the 3 months period by study personnel.

At the end of the study, the smartwatch will be returned to the study centre and all apps will be uninstalled. If a participant is not able to return the smartwatch, they will be provided with a shipping envelope.

Description of the smartwatch

The Withings ScanWatch acquires 3-axis raw accelerometer data and raw multi-wavelength (green, red, infrared) photoplethysmography (PPG). It bears a CE mark but is not a medicinal product. Data will be transferred to the Withings app and uploaded to the Withings server. Each participant will be provided with a study-specific email address that will be used for registration, so their personal email address will not be shared with Withings. The raw data will be transferred from the Withings server to the dBM-DEV study server through the Withings Advanced Research API. Withings servers are located in BSO data centres in France. Measures for data security are described below.

ScanWatch smartphone

Withings app

Description of the study app

The dBM-DEV study app was developed by Squaredev (Brussels, Belgium). It will be installed on the participants' personal smartphone. The study ID will be used for registration. No personal data (name, phone number, ...) will be stored in the app or transmitted to the study cloud. The study is available in three languages for the participant to choose: English, French, German, Spanish. Screenshots are shown in English.

Sign in

Sign in with the provided credentials

Study ID

Password

Sign in

Home

My daily tasks

- Morning question**
- Motor function test**
Acquire a video during a specific movement sequence. >
- Show all tasks (3)** >

Upcoming tasks

- Memory test**
Remember the image shown in the previous step. >
- Reaction test**
Respond rapidly or withhold a response. >
- Balloon challenge**
Pump up the balloon, but watch out before it breaks. >
- Show all tasks (3)** >

Study overview

- 15 days in study**
This study ends at 31/12/2023

35%
- 10 of 15 days of data uploaded**
5 days of data are missing

67%
- 6 of 6 tasks completed**
No task is missed. Well done!

100%
- Show details** >

HomeMenuRefreshProfile

Every two weeks, patients will be asked to acquire, with the help of their care partners, a short video of themselves while they perform a motor function test (45° angle, see screenshots below): Participants should sit on the chair and place both feet on the floor. First, tap each leg separately ten times. Next, with hands placed on the chest, participants should rise from the chair, maintain a standing position for 5 seconds. Lastly, they should take three steps forward, turn around, and return to the initial standing position. The sequence concludes with the participants returning to the seated position.

← **Motor function test**

- 1** Leg agility
Arising from chair
- 2** Posture >
- 3** Gait >

Sit on the chair and position the phone on a level surface directly in front of you on a stand, roughly 1 meter away, forming 45 degrees angle with the camera. When prepared, tap "Next" to initiate the test.

Continue

Motor test recorded

Well done

Repeat

Exit

Sit on the chair with both feet on the floor. Tap each leg 10 times quickly, separately. Then, stand from the chair with your hands on chest and maintain a standing position for 5 seconds. Take 3 steps forward, turn around, return to starting position, and sit back down slowly to complete the sequence.

Back

Start test

Moreover, patients will be asked to perform three brief cognitive tasks:

The N-back task examines working memory (Kirchner 1958). The subject is presented with a sequence of stimuli, and the task consists of indicating when the current stimulus matches the one from 1 step (generally n steps) earlier in the sequence. The response is indicated by tapping either the green or the red button on the screen.

← **Memory test**

In this experiment you will always be shown one of the following images.

Your task is to assess whether the current image is the same as the last image shown. Please always tap the **left button** if the current image is the same as the last one shown. If not, please tap the **right button**.

Start experiment

The balloon analogue risk task (BART) is a computerised decision-making task that is used to assess risk-taking behaviour (Lejuez et al. 2002). During the task, a participant is presented with 90 balloons of 3 different colours. The balloons appear one at a time. Participants are required to click a button labelled 'Balloon Pump.' Each click on the balloon pump will increase the size of the balloon and accumulate 5 cents per click in a temporary bank. The participants are not shown the amount being accumulated in their temporary bank. At any time, the participant can press another tab, labelled 'Collect \$,' to transfer the collected money into a permanent bank. If the participant wishes to continue pumping the balloon, they can do so, until eventually, the balloon explodes, resulting in the temporary funds resetting to zero and the next balloon showing up. However, if the participant collects the money before the balloon explodes, they can see the amount earned on that particular balloon via the tab labelled 'Last Balloon.' The money in the permanent bank will not be lost when a balloon explodes. Overall, the BART measures the risk-taking behaviour of an individual by recording the average number of pumps for each balloon colour, the total amount of earnings, and the number of exploded balloons.

← Balloon challenge

By clicking on the button below the challenge will start.

Start challenge

In this experiment you will see a screen like the one above. You see a balloon pump with which you can inflate a balloon.

Continue

Tap the balloon pump to inflate the balloon. Each pump gives you one point.

Continue

For example, if you pumped 30 times, you have **theoretically** collected 30 points.

Continue

Attention: If you pump too much, the balloon will fly away and your points will be lost.

Continue

A pink arrow points from the pump illustration down to the 'Collect points' button.

Collect points

When you feel your balloon is sufficiently filled, save your points by tapping this button.

Your task is **to collect as many points as possible.**

Continue

Points: 0
Last round: 0
In total: 0

Collect points

The stop-signal task measures attention (Lappin and Eriksen 1966) and is influenced by dopaminergic signalling (Colzato et al. 2009; Choudhury et al. 2019) and has been applied in mobile form (He et al. 2022). The participant must respond to an arrow stimulus, by selecting one of two options, depending on the direction in which the arrow points. If an audio tone is present, the subject must withhold making that response (inhibition). The test consists of two parts: In the first part, the participant is introduced to the test and told to select the left-hand button when they see a left-pointing arrow and the right-hand button when they see a right-pointing arrow. There is one block of 16 trials for the participant to practise this. In the second part, the participant is told to continue selecting the buttons when they see the arrows but, if they hear an auditory signal (a beep), they should withhold their response and not select the button. The task uses a staircase design for the stop signal delay (SSD), allowing the task to adapt to the performance of the participant, narrowing in on the 50% success rate for inhibition.

In addition, the study app will be able to collect keystroke data while the participant uses a custom virtual keyboard, i.e., all typing-related data can be collected passively during the user's spontaneous key tapping activities. The keyboard was developed by the AI-PROGNOSIS partner Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH). This is an optional feature of the study app that can be turned on and off by the study participants. Study participants will be trained to set up and use the custom virtual keyboard at the beginning of the study. Specifically, the following data will be collected:

- The time the typing session started and ended
- Keyboard language
- Timestamps corresponding to the moment keys were tapped down
- Timestamps corresponding to the moment keys were released
- Normalized (0-1) maximum pressure applied for each key tap
- Absolute non-directional Euclidean distance (in millimetres) between two consecutive key-taps
- Flag denoting whether a key was long pressed
- Binary flag if sound key feedback is on
- Binary flag if vibration feedback is on; and in case it is the duration
- Binary flag if the long press pop-up menu is on
- Landscape or portrait orientation of the keyboard
- Number of times the backspace/delete key was tapped
- Timestamps corresponding to the moment space/delete was tapped down
- Timestamps corresponding to the moment space/delete was released

Noteworthy, the text typed by participants will not be captured.

Data from the smartphone will be transferred to the study cloud whenever the participant has access to wifi. An avatar will be fitted to each video after acquisition. Only the avatar will be stored and transferred to the study cloud. Video data will not be stored in the study app or transmitted to the study cloud.

Possible complications/risks

The active tests performed by patients during the study are not riskier than movements carried out during their daily routine. They can be discontinued at any time or omitted if deemed not feasible by the participant.

Withdrawal

Participants will be able to withdraw their consent at any time and without giving any reason. In such a case, data collected up to that point in time will be kept in a pseudonymized form and used for the purposes of the study, unless participants exercise their right under the GDPR for their data to be deleted.

Participants who withdraw from the study or do not adhere to study procedures, e.g., do not use the smartphone app or the smartwatch, do not complete the questionnaires, or change their medication without authorisation from the investigator, will be replaced by recruiting new subjects.

EVALUATION CRITERIA

7.1. Main evaluation criterion

As an outcome measure, we will determine in study participants with high RBDSQ score the number nights with features that in the development cohort correlated with the occurrence of RBD episodes.

We expect these RBD-associated features to be more common in participants with a high RBDSQ score (7-12 points) than in participants with a low RBDSQ score (3-6 points). We also expect RBD-associated features to be more common in participants in which RBD is diagnosed by polysomnography than in participants in which this diagnosis is not made.

The study will be considered positive if the following conditions are met:

- RBD-associated features are observed in all participants with an RBDSQ score above the threshold of 6 points and a diagnosis of RBD in polysomnography.
- RBD-associated features are not observed in participants with an RBDSQ score below the threshold of 6 points and no diagnosis of RBD in polysomnography.
- RBD-associated features are not observed in at least 40% of participants with an RBDSQ score above the threshold of 6 points but no diagnosis of RBD in polysomnography.

In this case, we will conclude that the new dBM can potentially be used to detect RBD with higher **specificity** than the RBDSQ.

7.2. Secondary evaluation criteria

1. In extension to the main evaluation criterion, we will conclude that the new dBM can potentially be used to detect RBD with higher **sensitivity** than the RBDSQ if the following criteria are met:
 - RBD-associated features as defined by dBM tracking are observed in all participants with an RBDSQ score above the threshold of 6 points and a diagnosis of RBD in polysomnography.
 - RBD-associated features are not observed in participants with an RBDSQ score below the threshold of 6 points and no diagnosis of RBD in polysomnography.
 - RBD-associated features are not observed in at least 20% of participants with an RBDSQ score above the threshold of 6 points but no diagnosis of RBD in polysomnography.
2. With respect to the dBM for daytime somnolence, we will define mobility patterns (features) based on smartphone accelerometer data in the development cohort that correlate with the ESS score. In the confirmation cohort, we will measure the extent of the same features. Spearman correlation coefficients with the ESS score will be calculated for these features. This secondary end point will be considered met if the correlation is significant ($p < 0.05$) with $r^2 > 0.70$.
3. To verify feasibility for dBM assessment of bradykinesia, dyskinesias and tremor, we will quantify the amount of time that the smartwatch was worn, and the duration of the custom virtual keyboard usage during each day of the study and whether known motor signatures of bradykinesia, dyskinesias and tremor can be extracted from the data. As exploratory endpoints, we will determine the correlation between dBM and the corresponding score of the MDS-UPDRS obtained during the baseline visit.
4. To verify feasibility for dBM assessment of posture and gait, we will determine the number of videos acquired and their quality. Specifically, we will determine whether an avatar can be fitted to the videos. As an exploratory endpoint, we will correlate the obtained dBM score with the score obtained by a trained human rater.
5. To verify feasibility for dBM assessment of cognitive performance, we will determine the number of completed cognitive tasks. As an exploratory endpoint, we will determine whether task results correlate to the cognitive performance as assessed by MoCA during the baseline visit.

6. With respect to age and sex, all correlations listed above will be repeated with correction for age and sex. This is an exploratory readout.

CONDUCTING the research

The research schedule

Development cohort:

- Duration of the recruitment period: 6 months
- Follow-up period per participant: 4 weeks
- Total research duration: 7 months

Confirmation cohort:

- Duration of the recruitment period: 6 months
- Follow-up period per participant: 3 months
- Total research duration: 9 months

Summary table of the participant follow-up

Development cohort

	Screening	Baseline ³	During 4 weeks period ⁴
Informed consent	X		
Inclusion / exclusion criteria	X		
Sex	X		
Demographics ¹		X	
RBDSQ		X	
ESS		X	
PD clinical information ²		X	
MDS-UPDRS I-IV		X	
PDQ-8		X	
Install App		X	
Hand out smartphone		X	
Smartwatch accelerometer data			Continually (as much as possible, allow time for charging the device)
Active motor tests			Every two weeks (+/- two days)
Cognitive tests			Every two weeks (+/- two days)
Polysomnography			Once ⁵ (scheduling based on availability)
Question about previous night			Once daily at time specified by user
Keystroke data			Optional, when using the custom virtual keyboard

1) age, sex, education, handedness

2) For participants with PD only: year of first symptom, year of introduction of antiparkinsonian treatments, PD subtype, more strongly affected side, medication schedule

3) Screening and baseline can be on the same day. Maximum delay between Screening and baseline is 4 weeks.

4) Delay between baseline and end of study is 4 weeks +/- 7 days

5) If one of the first two participants per site.

Confirmation cohort

	Screening	Baseline ³	During 3 months period ⁴
Informed consent	X		
Inclusion / exclusion criteria	X		
Sex	X		
MoCA	X		
RBDSQ	X		
Demographics ¹		X	
PD clinical information ²		X	
MDS-UPDRS I-IV		X	
PDQ-8		X	
ESS		X	
Install App		X	
Hand out smartphone		X	
Smartwatch accelerometer data			Continually (as much as possible, allow time for charging the device)
Active motor tests			Every two weeks (+/- two days)
Cognitive tests			Every two weeks (+/- two days)
Polysomnography			Once (scheduling based on availability)
Question about previous night			Once daily at time specified by user
Keystroke data			Optional, when using the custom virtual keyboard

1) age, sex, education, handedness

2) year of first symptom, year of introduction of antiparkinsonian treatments, PD subtype, more strongly affected side, medication schedule

3) Screening and baseline can be on the same day. Maximum delay between Screening and baseline is 4 weeks.

4) Delay between baseline and end of study is 3 months +/- 7 days

Information of the persons concerned

The doctor will invite the patient to participate in this research and will inform him/her of the objective, the digital processing of data concerning the patient that will be collected during this research and will also specify the patient's rights of access, opposition and rectification to these data.

The doctor will also check the eligibility criteria. If the patient agrees to participate, he/she will orally give his/her consent and his/her non-opposition is documented in his/her medical file. The participant may, at any time, object to the use of his/her data as part of the research.

STATISTICAL ASPECTS

Calculation of study size

This is an exploratory study, and we have insufficient data for a precise sample size estimation.

Previous studies investigating sensitivity of the RBDSQ included 54 and 30 patients with RBD^{9,19}. We will use comparable numbers for the development cohort and include 30 patients with confirmed RBD and 30 controls that are matched for age and sex.

The sample size of 30 patients for the confirmation cohort is based on the number of realistic polysomnography investigations performed at each site, the available resources and polysomnography capacities.

Statistical methods employed

Primary evaluation criteria

We will determine the number of nights with RBD-associated dBM features.

The study will be considered positive if the following conditions are met:

1. RBD-associated features are observed in all participants with an RBDSQ score above the threshold of 6 points and a diagnosis of RBD in polysomnography.
2. RBD-associated features are not observed in participants with an RBDSQ score below the threshold of 6 points and no diagnosis of RBD in polysomnography.
3. RBD-associated features are not observed in at least 40% of participants with an RBDSQ score above the threshold of 6 points but no diagnosis of RBD in polysomnography.

Rationale for choosing these conditions:

The sensitivity of the RBDSQ is stated in the literature as 96% (Stiasny-Kolster et al. 2007; Halsband et al. 2018). We therefore expect that all patients with RBD in polysomnography will also have a positive RBDSQ score of >6 points. The new digital biomarker should have the same good sensitivity as the RBDSQ. Therefore, the first criterion for a positive study

is that the digital biomarker is also detectable in all patients in whom RBD can be detected on polysomnography (and an RBDSQ score >6 is to be expected).

The specificity of the RBDSQ is cited as 56%. We therefore expect that about half of the patients without RBD will show an RBDSQ score of >6 points in the polysomnography and the other half <6 points. As the specificity of the new digital biomarker should not be lower than that of the RBDSQ, the second criterion for a positive study is that of the patients without RBD who are correctly categorised by the RBDSQ (score <6), the digital biomarker is (also) undetectable.

As the specificity of the new digital biomarker should be higher than that of the RBDSQ, the third criterion is that the digital biomarker is not detectable in at least 40% of patients without RBD who are not correctly categorised by the RBDSQ (false-positive RBDSQ score >6).

This increase by 40% was chosen as follows to obtain a statistically significant improvement of diagnostic accuracy as determined by McNemar's test.

The prevalence of RBD in patients with Parkinson's disease is 25%. Of the 30 participants included in the Confirmation Cohort, 7 probably will have RBD and 23 will not have RBD. Due to the high sensitivity of the RBDSQ, all 7 participants with RBD are expected to have an RBDSQ score >6 , and following criterion 1, they will be dBM-positive. Among the 23 participants without RBD, the above numbers suggest that 10 will have a (false-positive) RBDSQ score >6 and 13 will have a (correct-negative) RBDSQ score <6 .

The following table summarizes these numbers assuming that n participants that are false-positive in RBDSQ will be (correctly) negative in the dBM.

	RBDSQ correct	RBDSQ incorrect
dBM correct	20 (7 positive ¹ + 13 negative)	n
dBM incorrect	0	10-n

Whether a change in the detection of an RBD is statistically significant can now be compared with the McNemar test with $c = \text{RBDSQ-positive, dBM negative}$; $b = \text{RBDSQ-negative, dBM positive}$:

n	$\chi^2 = (b-c)^2/(b+c)$	Evaluation
1	1	n.s.
2	2	n.s.
3	3	n.s.
4	4	$p < 0.05$
5	5	$p < 0.05$

At 5% error probability and 1 degree of freedom, values χ^2 above 3.84 are statistically significant.

Hence, based on the McNemar test, dBM will represent a statistically significant improvement if at least 4 of the 10 patients (40%) with false-positive RBDSQ are negative in the digital biomarker.

Secondary evaluation criteria

1. Similarly, we will determine whether the following criteria are met:
 - RBD-associated features as defined by dBM tracking are observed in all participants with an RBDSQ score above the threshold of 6 points and a diagnosis of RBD in polysomnography.
 - RBD-associated features are not observed in participants with an RBDSQ score below the threshold of 6 points and no diagnosis of RBD in polysomnography.
 - RBD-associated features are not observed in at least 20% of participants with an RBDSQ score above the threshold of 6 points but no diagnosis of RBD in polysomnography.
2. We will measure the frequency of features associated with daytime somnolence in the development cohort. Spearman correlation coefficients with the ESS score will be calculated. This secondary end point will be considered met if the correlation is significant ($p < 0.05$) with $r^2 > 0.70$.
3. We will quantify the amount of time that the smartwatch was worn during each day of the study and whether known motor signatures of bradykinesia, dyskinesias and tremor can be extracted from the data.
4. We will quantify the duration of the custom virtual keyboard usage during each day of the study and whether bradykinesia and rigidity can be assessed from the keystroke dynamics data.
5. We will determine the number of videos acquired and whether an avatar can be fitted to the videos.
6. All correlations listed above will be repeated with correction for age and sex.

Exploratory analyses

1. We will measure the frequency of features associated with bradykinesia, tremor and dyskinesias in both cohorts. Spearman correlation coefficients with the score of the MDS-UPDRS item will be calculated for these features. This secondary end point will be considered met if the correlation is significant ($p < 0.05$) with $r^2 > 0.70$.
2. Trained raters will manually score the acquired motion patterns. An algorithm trained in the development will also score the acquired motion patterns. Spearman correlation coefficients between the two scores will be calculated. This set of secondary end points will be considered met if the correlation is significant ($p < 0.05$) with $r^2 > 0.70$.

3. Features obtained from the smartphone-based cognitive tests will be determined from both cohorts, pooled and correlated to the MoCA of the same participant at baseline. This set of secondary end points will be considered met if the correlation is significant ($p < 0.05$) with $r^2 > 0.70$.
4. Features derived from the analysis of keystroke dynamic analysis will be determined from both cohorts. Spearman correlation coefficients to clinical scores for bradykinesia and rigidity will be calculated.

Rights of access to data and source documents

Legal basis of data processing

Participants will provide written informed consent for all acquisition, storage and processing of data. If participants withdraw consent, the data will be deleted.

Only personal data will be recorded that is strictly necessary for an outcome or for the quality control of the research.

Subjects may request the deletion of their data at any time, even without giving reasons. Data that have already been included in evaluations or have been anonymised can no longer be deleted.

Moreover, for the purposes of ensuring personal data protection and integrity, a data processing agreement has been signed between the partners, defining the data that will be processed, the envisaged processing operations, the allocation of tasks and operations between the partners, possible data transfers between the partners, the envisaged storage period of the data, the implemented technical and organisational measures.

All data collected is for scientific purposes only. The findings from this research project will be published exclusively in an anonymised form. It is ensured that the re-identification of individual patients is not possible.

Access to data

Agreeing to participate in the protocol implies that the people who carry out the research will make the documents and personal data that are strictly necessary for the monitoring, quality control and auditing of the research, available in accordance with the laws and regulations in force.

Source data

All information contained in original documents, or in authenticated copies of these documents, relating to clinical examinations, observations or other activities conducted as part of a research and necessary for the reconstruction and evaluation of the research. The documents in which the source data are saved are called the source documents.

The following data are considered source data:

- Informed consent
- Patient questionnaires

All other data are digital data or entered into the eCRF directly:

- Presence or absence of inclusion and exclusion criteria
- Demographics
- PD clinical information (for participants with a diagnosis of PD)
- Smartwatch accelerometer and heart activity data
- Keystroke data captured by the custom virtual keyboard
- Data recorded during active tests on the smartphone

Data confidentiality

In accordance with the legislative provisions in force, persons having direct access to source data will take all the necessary precautions to ensure the confidentiality of information relating to research, to participants, especially as regards their identity and the results obtained. These people, like the people who direct and monitor the research, are subject to professional secrecy.

All data stored in eCRF and all digital data is codified. The names of the persons concerned, or their addresses are never mentioned.

Participants will be assigned a study-specific pseudonym upon inclusion, which does not allow any inference to their person ("TUD" and random number). The list for identifying patients (enrolment log) is stored exclusively on the study PI's local computer and is not passed on to cooperation partners. Access to the enrolment log is limited to the local study team, i.e., employees of TUD financed by the Horizon AI-PROGNOSIS project.

At the end of the study, the data that allows identification of a participant (enrolment log) will be deleted. The records are then anonymised and will be kept in this form indefinitely. The data subjects will be also informed regarding this final processing operation.

The sponsor will ensure that each research participant has been informed of access to the individual data concerning them and strictly necessary for the quality control of the research.

Quality control and quality assurance

Guidelines for collecting data

For each participant enrolled, an eCRF must be completed and signed by the principal Investigator or authorised (PI-delegated) from the study staff. The Investigator should ensure the accuracy, completeness and timeliness of the data in the eCRFs and in all required reports. A clinical research technician will enter the data into the eCRF database created by the data manager in charge of the study. dBM data will be collected via smartwatch and smartphone. An explanation must be provided for any missing data.

Management of the research

Research will be conducted by the investigator in accordance with a clinical research technician (study coordinator). This technician will be in charge of:

- logistics and the organisation of the patients visits (calls and preparation of study procedures)
- reporting on the study progress to the sponsor
- completing the case report form (request for additional information, corrections, etc.),
- participating in monitoring visits with the Clinical Research Associate appointed by the sponsor.

The clinical research technician will work in accordance with the standard operating procedures (GCP).

Monitoring of the research

The Sponsor or the Sponsor's representative will conduct a site visit to verify the qualifications of each investigator, inspect the site facilities, and inform the investigator of responsibilities and the procedures for ensuring adequate and correct documentation.

The investigator is required to prepare and maintain adequate and accurate case histories designed to record all observations and other data pertinent to the study for each study participant. All information recorded on the eCRFs for this study must be consistent with the patients' source documentation (i.e., medical records).

Monitoring and auditing procedures developed by the Sponsor or the Sponsor's representative will be followed in order to comply with GCP guidelines. On-site checking of the eCRFs for completeness and clarity, cross-checking with source documents, and clarification of administrative matters will be performed.

A clinical researcher appointed by the sponsor who is not directly involved in the study will regularly visit the study team, during the implementation of the research, one or more times during research.

- after enrolment of the first participant
- in accordance with the risk-based monitoring plan during the course of the study
- at the end of the study

During these visits and in accordance with the risk-based monitoring plan, the following elements will be reviewed:

- informed consent,
- compliance with the research protocol and the procedures defined therein,
- quality of the data collected in the case report form: accuracy, missing data, consistency of the data with the source documents

All visits will be the subject of a monitoring report by written report.

Data management

Electronic case report form (eCRF)

Open Clinica will be used for the eCRF. Data will be entered into the eCRF by qualified and delegated site personnel (clinicians or study coordinator of the site).

Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, the coordinator of the overarching Horizon AI-PROGNOSIS project, will be responsible for hosting and maintaining the database on a server located in France.

TUD will be in charge of data management for this study. The data manager will generate a validation plan that will have to be approved by the scientific council of the study. After data capture, with the help of AUTH, the data manager will generate a set of validation tests that will aim at verifying respect of inclusion / exclusion criteria, identifying missing data, checking chronologic consistency when several dates are considered, and highlighting aberrant data. Following these tests, a set of queries will be sent to the investigators for verification and whenever it is possible for correction. Then, the database will be corrected accordingly, before locking the database for data analysis.

Means of security

Infrastructure security features that could be implemented include: firewall protection of infrastructure servers, DDoS attack protection, authenticated access to infrastructure servers, identity and access management of services/tools, reverse proxy configuration for services/tools, encrypted and secure communication with infrastructure servers and deployed tools, hard disk encryption of infrastructure servers if required, backups and snapshots of infrastructure servers, Hetzner-provided additional security features (data centres certified according to ISO/IEC 27001)

Management of access right

The management of access rights will be enforced with the deployment of an authentication-authorization server, like Keycloak. There, each user will be assigned with a study-specific pseudonym/account and a corresponding password that could be set to respect enhanced security rules, e.g., 8 characters minimum, containing at least three of specific character types such as upper case, lower case, numbers and/or special characters etc.

Backups and snapshots of infrastructure servers

Hetzner, the cloud provider, offers backups of the VMs hosting the servers periodically, on a daily time basis. For each server, there are seven slots for backups kept in Hetzner servers. If all slots are full, the oldest backup will be deleted. The backups are kept in Hetzner servers in the same geographic location as the cloud server they were created from, but usually in a different data centre. In addition, Hetzner offers custom snapshots whose creation and deletion is not automatic and can be initiated only by the user/customer. Snapshots are automatically in a different location than the cloud server they were created from but in the same network zone.

Audit and inspection

An audit may be conducted at any time by persons appointed by the sponsor and independent of the persons conducting the research. Its purpose is to verify the participants' safety and respect for their rights, compliance with applicable regulations and the reliability of data.

An inspection can also be carried out by a competent authority (e.g., EMA in the context of a European study).

The audit, as well as the inspection, can be applied at all stages of the research, from the development of the protocol to the publication of the results and the classification of the data used or produced as part of the research.

Investigators agree to comply with the sponsor's requirements as regards an audit and the competent authority for a research inspection.

Ethical AND REGULATORY considerations

Compliance with reference texts

The planning, implementation and use of the project and the project results will be in accordance with the relevant ethical and scientific standards. During the course of the study, the partners will respect the fundamental principles of research integrity, as set out in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, thus respecting human dignity and integrity, ensuring honesty and transparency towards research subjects and by receiving freely provided and informed consent (as well as assent whenever relevant), protecting vulnerable people, ensuring privacy and confidentiality, promoting justice and inclusiveness, minimising harm and maximising benefit and sharing the benefits with disadvantaged populations or any people who will be benefited by its findings and results.

The applicants thus undertake to comply with the requirements of the Memorandum on Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice of the German Research Foundation (DFG), the Declaration of Helsinki and Memorandum III "Methods for Health Services Research" (Dietrich et al., 2010) of the German Network for Health Services Research, the State or Federal Data Protection Act and the General Data Protection Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council (Regulation EU 2016/679 - GDPR). In addition, the clinically active colleagues involved follow the professional regulations for physicians of the responsible state medical association in the respective current versions.

The study plan is submitted to the Ethics Committee of the University Hospital Dresden for consultation before the start of the study.

The names of the patients and all other confidential information are subject to the medical confidentiality obligation of the attending physicians and the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation and the Federal Data Protection Acts (DSGVO and BDSG new).

Benefit-Risk ratio

No risks are expected for participating in this study, Participants have no direct benefit from participating in the study except for the control group for which detection of paradoxical sleep disorder is possible. Moreover, participating in a research study can increase self-efficacy and sense of control for study participants.

Constraints related to the research and possible compensation of participants

Participants are not allowed to enrol simultaneously in other intervention trials and will be notified accordingly. They will be allowed to enrol in other trials as soon as their enrolment in the current study comes to an end. The only constraint for patients is having to wear the watch day and night, and having to complete the tests required as part of the study protocol. Participants only travel once to the centre, at study initiation, except for 1) participants whose screening and baseline visits cannot be performed on the same day, and 2) patients who carry out a polysomnography, which is performed on a separate visit.

Participants who complete the entire study will receive a compensation of €100.

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Staff Training for dBM-DEV study

1. Tasks of study teams

1.1. Recruitment

The aim of dBM-DEV is to develop and test digital biomarkers - using smartwatch and smartphone - that detect and quantify important aspects of Parkinson's disease. To accomplish this, participants install a study app on their smartphone (mAI-Health app) and wear a smartwatch.

The dBM-DEV study consists of two cohorts and recruits three types of participants:

- development cohort
 - participants with confirmed RBD (to be recruited first)
 - matched healthy controls (recruited after RBD participants)
- confirmation cohort
 - participants with PD and unknown RBD status

The full list of inclusion and exclusion criteria can be found in the study protocol.

Most important criteria:

- all study participants need to have a compatible smartphone (*Android 11 or higher, which means the phone is from 2020 or newer*)
- participants in the RBD cohort and in the PD cohort need to have a partner with whom they share the bedroom at night - to help with the "morning question" about RBD during last night's sleep.
- In participants of the RBD cohort, RBD needs to be documented by polysomnography prior to inclusion in the study.
- Control participants need to be matched to the RBD cohort -> demographics will be given out by the WP5 meeting as we go.
- Participants in the PD cohort need to have a borderline score in the RBD screening questionnaire.

Full criteria:

"Development cohort", inclusion criteria for participants with RBD

- Age: >18 years
- Written declaration of informed consent (**see Annex 3**).
- The participant is using a smartphone compatible with the smartwatch that will be provided for the duration of the study.
- The participant is able to use the smartphone, smartwatch and study app – as judged by investigator
- Wifi available at the participant's home to upload smartwatch data.

- Known RBD as defined by the *International Classification of Sleep Disorders (ICSD-3)* (Sateia 2014) confirmed by polysomnography
- The participant has a partner with whom they share their bedroom at night
- Ability to provide information after each night whether an RBD episode occurred, with the help of their partner
- At least one episode of RBD per week (on average over the last month).
- A diagnosis of PD is not required.

“Development cohort”, inclusion criteria for controls

- Age (+/- 5 years)- and sex-matched control for a participant with known RBD
- Age: >18 years
- Written declaration of informed consent (see Annex 4).
- The participant is using a smartphone compatible with the smartwatch that will be provided for the duration of the study.
- The participant is able to use the smartphone, smartwatch and study app – as judged by investigator
- Wi-Fi available at the participant’s home to upload smartwatch data.

“Confirmation cohort”, inclusion criteria for participants

- Age: >18 years.
- Diagnosis of PD based on the criteria published by the Movement Disorders Society (Postuma et al. 2015)
- Absence of dementia (defined as MoCA score ≥ 24) to ensure compliance with study procedures and ability to consent for study procedures. MoCA: Montreal Cognitive Assessment (Nasreddine et al. 2005)
- Written declaration of informed consent (see Annex 5)
- The participant is using a smartphone compatible with the smartwatch that will be provided for the duration of the study
- The participant has a care partner
- The participant is able to use the smartphone, smartwatch and study app – as judged by investigator
- RBDSQ score 3 - 12 points (Stiasny-Kolster et al. 2007)
- The medication for PD and sleep has not been changed during the past 4 weeks.

Exclusion criteria, all cohorts

- Inability to consent for study procedures, e.g., due to cognitive decline, as judged by the investigator.
- Lacking motivation to participate in study procedures – as judged by the investigator.
- Participants who are not affiliated to their country’s social security health system
- Participant under adult autonomy protection system, legal guardianship or

incapacitation.

Note that there are separate informed consent forms (ICFs) for each cohort and for the care partner.

1.2. Contents of the ICF and informed consent

Follow local SOPs.

1.3. Definition and handling of source data, data entry

Follow local SOPs.

Use of OpenClinica has been trained (see Appendix for quick start guide).

Access OpenClinica via this link: <https://openclinica.ai-prognosis.eu/>

The credentials for each account are the same with those used in the mock data entry.

The smartwatch data and data collected from the smartphone are considered source data. To fulfill regulatory requirements, the reports of raw data upload will be filed with the study documents at the study sites.

1.4. Tracking of data upload

The smartwatch raw data constitutes the most important information acquired during the study. It is uploaded to the AI-PROGNOSIS Cloud through the mAI-Health app. For this to work, the study participants need to have their smartphone with them or in close proximity (< 10 m) as much as possible.

The AI-PROGNOSIS technical partners (SQD, INTRA) will provide a report for study teams to know which data has been successfully uploaded.

1.5. Making sure that study participants know all required features of their phone

To make sure that the study participant can use the digital devices during the study, the study team should ask the study participant during the baseline visit to conduct the following list of tasks:

- connect phone and watch to the charger(s)
- connect the phone to the local Wi-Fi in the institution
- open the AI-PROGNOSIS webpage, go to the FAQs section (once this has been created)

- close the mAI-Health app (close, not hide) and re-open the mAI-Health app
- restart the smartphone

It is in the eye of the study team to judge based on the performance of the participant whether the participant will be able to complete the study. If the study participant is not able to complete these tasks, additional training might be required, or the participant should be excluded from the study.

1.6. Installing the study app and connecting the smartwatch

Follow the mAI-Health app manual (see Appendix).
The study will be available on the Google Play store.

The usernames and passwords for participants (app sign-in) for each site can be found [here: \(https://aristotleuniversity.sharepoint.com/sites/AI-PROGNOSIS627/Shared%20Documents/Forms/AllItems.aspx?id=%2Fsites%2FAI%2DPROGNOSIS627%2FShared%20Documents%2FWP4%20The%20AI%2DPROGNOSIS%20digital%20health%20ecosystem%2FT4%2E3%20Data%20storage%20and%20analytics%20infrastructure%2FUser%20Accounts&viewid=2ccaa0ed%2D2208%2D40c5%2Dab61%2D0d09d035aef7\)](https://aristotleuniversity.sharepoint.com/sites/AI-PROGNOSIS627/Shared%20Documents/Forms/AllItems.aspx?id=%2Fsites%2FAI%2DPROGNOSIS627%2FShared%20Documents%2FWP4%20The%20AI%2DPROGNOSIS%20digital%20health%20ecosystem%2FT4%2E3%20Data%20storage%20and%20analytics%20infrastructure%2FUser%20Accounts&viewid=2ccaa0ed%2D2208%2D40c5%2Dab61%2D0d09d035aef7)

1.7. Handing out study equipment

Participant should be handed out

- the smartwatch with booklet and charging cable
- the wall adapter for charging the smartwatch
- a stand for video acquisition during the motor assessment test
- packaging to send back the smartwatch and rest of the equipment at the end of the study

1.8. Troubleshooting and contact information

- First, consult the FAQ page on the AI-PROGNOSIS website

Contact information for specific topics

	Name	Email
General questions	Björn Falkenburger	bfalken@ukdd.de
Study app (mAI-Health app)	John Zaras	john.zaras@squaredev.io
OpenClinica	Ioannis Gerasimou	gerasimoi@ece.auth.gr
User accounts for study	Theodora Brisimi	Theodora.BRISIMI@netcompan

app (mAI-Health app)		y.com
Cognitive tests	Tim Feige	Tim.Feige@ukdd.de
Motor tests	Sofia Dias	sbalula@fmh.ulisboa.pt
Research keyboard (custom virtual keyboard)	Ioannis Gerasimou	gerasimoi@ece.auth.gr

2. Trainings for study participants, to be given by study teams at baseline

2.1. Question in the morning about RBD episode during last night's sleep

Each morning, the mAI-Health app will ask whether an RBD episode has occurred during last night's sleep. Participants will receive a notification to answer the question the next morning, one hour after the time they logged in the app that they usually wake up (during the onboarding process). The question should not be answered by the study participant alone, but rather after consulting with the bedroom partner.

What are signs of an RBD episode?

- Vivid dreams with aggressive or action-packed content
- Sudden movement of arms or legs during sleep, like fights, sometimes (almost) hurting their bed partner or so that things fall down around the bed (lamp, book, glasses)
- Speaking, shouting, swearing or laughing loudly
- Complex movements, gestures like waving, saluting, chasing mosquitoes.
- Falling out of bed
- Movements awaken the participant, and the participant remembers the dream

2.2. Custom keyboard (*in study sites approved*)

The custom keyboard ('Research keyboard') that comes with the mAI-Health app should be activated and set up, with the participant's consent. This can be done during the app onboarding process or later through the Settings of the app (see app manual for details).

- It should be explained to the participant that the use of the Research keyboard allows for collecting data related to the way they use the keys. This will be done for assessing motor and cognitive function. The characters typed are not collected.
- The participant should be made aware that the Research keyboard will replace their current keyboard.
- It should be explained to the participant that the keyboard may not have all the functionalities that their current keyboard has and that it may take some time to get used to it.

- The participant should be informed that they can deactivate the keyboard through the Settings of the device (see app manual for details).

2.3. Motor assessment test (video acquisition)

Details will follow, including where to acquire the videos (home, hallway, garden, ...) and how to record correctly (recording distance, angle etc.)

Conduct one practice run at study site at baseline

Stand should be provided to study participants.

Care partners should start the video.

2.4. Cognitive tests

Will follow, in particular

- when and where to perform them
- short description of the tests; especially of Stop-Signal (so that participants don't feel bad about mistakes)
- conduct one practice run for each test at study site at baseline

2.5. Using the smartwatch

Smartwatches should be charged every day at midday (to have full power during the night), for instance at lunch time.

Participants should wear the smartwatch as much as possible, in particular during the night.

Participants with PD should wear the smartwatch on the arm that is more strongly affected by Parkinson's disease. If both arms are similarly affected, participants with PD should wear the smartwatch on the dominant hand. Controls and non-PD RBD patients should wear the smartwatch on the dominant hand. The arm on which they wear the smartwatch should be entered into the appropriate eCRF in OpenClinica. The smartwatch should be worn comfortably but not loose, because it may lower the quality of the motion and pulse data captured.

Participants should have their phone with them or in close proximity (< 10 m) as much as possible to allow data transfer from the smartwatch to the phone.

The study team will monitor data upload and contact the participant in case of problems.

The participant can contact the study team any time through email (in the App) in case of problems.

2.6. Using the study app (mAI-Health app)

See manual in Appendix

2.7. Closing the study

At the end of the study, the participants should

- uninstall the study app (see app manual) and
- bring or send back smartwatch and charger

Study staff will send an email to Theodora Brisimi (Theodora.BRISIMI@netcompany.com) to deactivate data collection for the participant.

3. Assessments at baseline

3.1. Duration of the study

Development cohort:

- Duration of the recruitment period: 6 months
- Follow-up period per participant: 4 weeks
- Total research duration: 7 months

Confirmation cohort:

- Duration of the recruitment period: 6 months
- Follow-up period per participant: 3 months
- Total research duration: 9 months

3.2. Assessments

Development cohort

	Screening	Baseline ³	During 4 weeks period ⁴
Informed consent	X		
Inclusion / exclusion criteria	X		
Sex	X		
Demographics ¹		X	
RBDSQ		X	
ESS		X	
PD clinical information ²		X	

MDS-UPDRS I-IV		X	
PDQ-8		X	
Install App		X	
Hand out equipment		X	
Smartwatch data			Continuously (as much as possible, allow time for charging the device)
Active motor test			Every two weeks (+five days)
Cognitive tests			Every two weeks (+five days)
Polysomnography			Once ⁵ (scheduling based on availability)
Question about previous night's sleep			Once daily at time specified by user
Typing-related data			Optional, when using the custom virtual keyboard

1) age, sex, education, handedness

2) For participants with PD only: year of first symptom, year of introduction of antiparkinsonian treatments, PD subtype, more strongly affected side, medication schedule

3) Screening and baseline can be on the same day. Maximum delay between Screening and baseline is 4 weeks.

4) Delay between baseline and end of study is 4 weeks +/- 7 days

5) If one of the first two participants per site.

Confirmation cohort

	Screening	Baseline ³	During 3 months period ⁴
Informed consent	X		
Inclusion / exclusion criteria	X		
Sex	X		
MoCA	X		
RBDSQ	X		
Demographics ¹		X	

PD clinical information ²		X	
MDS-UPDRS I-IV		X	
PDQ-8		X	
ESS		X	
Install App		X	
Hand out equipment		X	
Smartwatch data			Continuously (as much as possible, allow time for charging the device)
Active motor test			Every two weeks (+five days)
Cognitive tests			Every two weeks (+five days)
Polysomnography			Once (scheduling based on availability)
Question about previous night's sleep			Once daily at time specified by user
Typing-related data			Optional, when using the custom virtual keyboard

1) age, sex, education, handedness

2) year of first symptom, year of introduction of antiparkinsonian treatments, PD subtype, more strongly affected side, medication schedule

3) Screening and baseline can be on the same day. Maximum delay between Screening and baseline is 4 weeks.

4) Delay between baseline and end of study is 3 months +/- 7 days

Appendices

1. OpenClinica manual: [AI-PROGNOSIS_OpenClinica_data_entry_quickstart.pdf](#)
2. mAI-Health app manual: [AI-PROGNOSIS_mAI-Health App User's Manual.docx](#)
3. ICF for participants with RBD
4. ICF for controls
5. ICF for participants with PD